

**Unveiling the Advantages of Master Plan Development
over Incremental Growth in Enhancing Property
Values for Residential Sector**

Unveiling the Advantages of Master Plan Development over Incremental Growth in Enhancing Property Values for Residential Sector

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Abstract

Numerous studies discuss how a property's design quality results in increased property value. These values may be economic, social, or environmental; Economical factors have been taken into account for the purpose of this study in order to analyze the increased property value that superior design in masterplan development may provide compared to incremental growth. Two case studies, one including masterplan-led development and the other incremental growth, were considered for this study.

This study is significant since developers, contractors, and investors undertake most of the development that occurs in the residential sector in India. As a result of the increased capital expenditure, their first concern will always be the project's economic feasibility. In order to accomplish economic, social, and environmental sustainability all at once, master plan-directed development can play a crucial role. Developers would invest in excellent quality design if they could profit from such interventions and if such efforts really increased property prices, increasing both social and environmental value.

The study therefore shows that these design attributes in masterplan-led development increase property value in the residential sector and how this may be advantageous for Indian urban growth.

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01

Introduction

Background of Research

The research aims to investigate various aspects of master plan development in relation to urban design qualities to determine their impact on property value. Additionally, the study will analyze existing urban design and planning practices to assess their influence on property values. The findings from this research will aid in improving urban design practices in India's development projects.

This research is useful for several reasons. Firstly, by investigating the benefits of urban design in India and its impact on residential property values, it aims to fill a gap in existing knowledge. The limited emphasis on urban design in India makes it crucial to provide evidence that supports the hypothesis of urban design qualities improving property value.

Secondly, the findings of this research can have implications for urban planning and development in India. If the hypothesis is proven, it would highlight the importance of incorporating urban design principles and qualities in residential projects. This could lead to more aesthetically pleasing and functional urban environments, enhancing the overall quality of life for residents.

Furthermore, demonstrating the positive relationship between urban design qualities and property value can attract attention from policymakers, real estate developers, and investors. It could serve as a catalyst for promoting and prioritizing urban design as an integral component of urban development strategies in India, ultimately leading to more sustainable and desirable urban spaces.

Lastly, this research can empower homeowners, buyers, and investors by providing valuable insights into the factors that contribute to property value. Understanding the impact of urban design qualities on property values can inform decision-making processes.

The findings of this research will provide valuable insights for urban planners, real estate developers, and policymakers, informing them about the importance of incorporating certain design qualities in urban development projects. Overall, this research holds significance in expanding knowledge, influencing urban planning practices, and empowering stakeholders in making informed decisions regarding urban design and residential property.

Research Question

Does urban design led master plan development in the residential sector lead to greater property value enhancement compared to incremental growth strategies?

Aim

The aim of this study is to explore the benefits of urban design-led master plan development in comparison to incremental growth approaches within the residential sector, specifically in terms of enhancing property values.

Objectives

Objective 1: To analyze and compare the approach of urban planning and design between the Indian context and the UK, focusing on the delivery of amenities and facilities in both regions.

Objective 2: Analyze the Role of Urban Design Qualities in Property Value Enhancement.

Objective 3: Compare Master Plan led Development and Incremental Growth Approaches to analyze Property Value Enhancement.

Hypothesis

It is hypothesized that urban design led master plan development in the residential sector yields a more substantial enhancement of property values compared to incremental growth strategies. This hypothesis is grounded in the belief that carefully planned and integrated design elements have a synergistic effect on property values beyond what can be achieved through piecemeal development.

Scope

The scope of this study encompasses an examination of urban design qualities and their impact on residential property values. The research will focus on major two urban areas in the UK, considering diverse urban design elements and their potential influence on property values. The research will explore different urban design aspects to understand how these qualities contribute to property value. The result of the research will help to enhance the urban design qualities in development across India.

Limitations

However, it is essential to acknowledge that the scope of the research might be limited by data availability, Constraints in data collection and time period for research. The study may also face challenges in quantifying the subjective aspects of urban design, as individual preferences and perceptions can vary significantly. Additionally, the study will not investigate the preferences and perceptions of residents and potential homebuyers towards urban design elements and their willingness to pay for properties with enhanced design qualities. Nevertheless, by providing insights into the benefits of urban design qualities on residential property values in India, the research can contribute to informed decision-making for urban planning, real estate development, and policy formulation in the country.

Research Method

Figure 1.1: Research Method
Source: Author's own illustrations

To carry out the study London has been looked at as a case study perspective to highlight the benefits of master plan led development. Next chapter explores the urban planning and design practices in both the UK and India.

02

*Urban
Planning and
Urban Design
Practices*

Overview of London Urban Planning Process

To understand the urban planning process in the UK, London has been taken as an example. The urban planning process in London involves several stages, starting from the citywide strategic level down to the more detailed plot level plans. Here's an overview of the process, from the London Plan to plot level planning:

	<p>1. NPPF – National Planning Policy Framework: The National Planning Policy Framework (NPPF) in London provides a comprehensive guide for planning and development decisions. It outlines the government's policies and principles to ensure sustainable and balanced growth in the city. This framework covers various aspects, such as housing, infrastructure, environment, and economic development. It aims to streamline planning processes, encourage sustainable design, and promote community engagement. The NPPF serves as a reference for local authorities, developers, and the public to achieve responsible urban development in London.</p>
	<p>2. London Plan: The London Plan is the overarching strategic document that sets out the vision, policies, and framework for the development and growth of London as a whole. It covers a wide range of topics including housing, transportation, environment, economy, culture, and more. The London Plan is developed by the Greater London Authority (GLA) and involves extensive consultation with stakeholders, local authorities, and the public.</p>
	<p>3. Borough Local Plans: Each of London's 32 boroughs is responsible for creating its own Local Plan that aligns with the policies and vision set out in the London Plan. The Borough Local Plan details the spatial and development strategies specific to that borough, taking into account local needs and characteristics. These plans identify land use designations, development allocations, and policies for areas within the borough.</p>
	<p>4. Area Action Plans and Master Plans: In some cases, areas within a borough may require more specific planning strategies. Area Action Plans or Masterplans are developed to guide the regeneration or development of particular districts, neighborhoods, or sites. These plans provide more detailed policies and design guidelines to shape the character, scale, and function of the area.</p>

	<p>5. Development Management and Planning Applications:</p> <p>At this stage, developers and property owners submit planning applications for specific projects, such as new buildings or significant renovations. These applications are reviewed by the local planning authority, which assesses them against the relevant policies, regulations, and guidelines. Public consultation may also be a part of this process, allowing community input on proposed developments. stages 6 & 7 are usually followed through an approved detail design which would show the appearance of the building(s) and floor plans.</p>
	<p>6. Detailed Planning and Design:</p> <p>Once planning permission is granted, the design process becomes more detailed. Architects and designers work on creating detailed plans and drawings that adhere to the approved scheme while addressing specific design considerations, such as building materials, landscaping, and sustainability features.</p>
	<p>7. Technical detailing and compliance (Plot Level Planning):</p> <p>Plot-level planning involves refining the details of a specific site, often at a very granular level. It includes aspects like building layout, façade design, access points, parking, landscaping, and other site-specific considerations. The aim is to ensure that the proposed development integrates well with its surroundings and follows the approved design principles. Technical detailing and compliance with the conditions attached to the permission will stipulate what needs further approval. It is usual to supply these sorts of details for approval before construction or in some cases during. Such as materials or landscape design.</p>

Figure 2.1: Urban Planning at different scale in London: Hierarchy of Plans - starting from city level plans to individual plot level development.

Source: Author's own illustrations

Throughout these stages, community engagement, public consultation, and collaboration with various stakeholders play a crucial role. Local residents, businesses, community groups, and other interested parties have the opportunity to provide feedback and influence the planning process at multiple levels.

It's important to note that the urban planning process can vary depending on the scale and complexity of the development, as well as the specific requirements of each borough or area within London. The process aims to balance the city's growth and development with its unique character, heritage, and the needs of its residents.

Overview of Indian Urban Planning Process

History

In India, town planning is nothing new. Stanislawski and Kostof attribute the world's first example of regular grid town planning to the Indus Valley Civilization of Ancient India, notably the city of Mohenjo-Daro in modern-day Pakistan, around 2,500 years before the birth of Christ (Yonekur, 1984). Archaeologists estimate that Mohenjo-Daro had roughly 35,000 inhabitants at its peak (Stanislawski, 1946). The city was located in the delta of the lower Indus basin (Stanislawski, 1946). This city's size was around 1km square. Mohenjo-daro prospered and lived for almost 500 years (from around 2500 B.C. to around 2000 B.C.), during which period it was subjected to catastrophic flooding and destructions, and it had to be restored or reconstructed several times, modifying its original layout here and there (Major, 2018).

Figure 2.2: Mohen-Jo-Daro City Plan, 2500 BC - plan shows the how planning had been done in Indian Cities.

Source: <https://architexturez.net/doc/green2006thesi>

Even in the Vedic era, towns and villages were planned in a scientific way (Kshirsagar, et al., 2004). The Shilpa Shastras, Niti Shastras, and Smriti Shastras, as well as the astrological and astronomical treatises, all explain the science of ancient urban design, urban planning and architecture (Kshirsagar, et al., 2004). In the Vedas, towns and villages are frequently described. Vedic culture made significant advancements in the design of towns and villages. The Shilpa Shastras' text reveals that urban planning and architectural issues were dealt with systematically (Kshirsagar, et al., 2004). It displays scientific understanding, systematic approach, and use of Shastras in town planning and construction structures. The Shilpa Shastras emphasized the need for urban planning initiatives to be carried out appropriately and rationally (Kshirsagar, et al., 2004). Within the confines of the rules established by the Shilpa Shastras, a person was permitted complete use of his imagination (Kshirsagar, et al., 2004). The Sthapati (Architect, Town Planner) and his staff were regarded

as members of the upper class because of their well-recognized profession. All necessary conditions for a thriving civic life were taken into consideration in ancient Indian town design (Kshirsagar, et al., 2004). It gives descriptions of the temples, the market, the streets and alleys, the royal palaces, the residences of the citizens, the arched gateways, the water storage sheds, the pleasure garden, the tanks and reservoirs, the wells, the city wall, the moats, the forts, etc (Kshirsagar, et al., 2004). In terms of layout, organization of public areas and public buildings, water supply, drainage, etc the River Valley Civilization, particularly the Indus Valley Civilization, has demonstrated a high degree of town design (Kshirsagar, et al., 2004).

(Vedic Era - The Vedic Age was between 1500 BC and 600 BC. This is the next major civilization that occurred in ancient India after the decline of the Indus Valley Civilization by 1400 BC. The Vedas were composed in this period and this gives this age the name. The Vedas are also the chief source of information about this era.)

Current Urbanization Scenario

According to Census of India 2011, In 2011, there were 1210 million people living in India, and the country's urbanization rate was 31.1% (Kumar, et al., 2021). Around 11% of the world's urban population lives in cities in India, making India the second-largest urban area in the world (MoHFW, 2020). In numerical terms, in comparison to many other highly urbanized nations India's urban population is higher (Kumar, et al., 2021). The nation has reached a turning point in the process of its economic change, in which half of India's population will be "urban" in a few decades (MoHFW, 2020). According to earlier projections, Urban population is expected to grow by 416 million people between 2018 and 2050 (United Nations 2018) and reach 50% urbanization by that time (UN-Habitat, 2017) in India. By 2036, urban growth is anticipated to account for 73% of the population increase (MoHFW, 2020).

India is undergoing an extraordinary second wave of urbanization. As per Nijman (2012), 53 new cities with populations of one million or more were added to India's urban population between the years 2001 and 2011, totaling 91 million new urban residents (Jain & Pallagst, 2015). The world's biggest and rapidly developing cities are found there (Jain & Pallagst, 2015). For instance, According to a UN-2014 report, cited by Jain & Pallagst (2015), Delhi and Mumbai will have 25 and 21 million residents respectively by 2030, making them the second and fourth biggest cities in the world.

Composition of Urban Population

Towns' governance status: According to the Census of 2011, India's urban system consists of 7933 settlements, which are primarily categorized as statutory (4041) and census (3892) towns (Kumar, et al., 2021). There are several settlements and outgrowths that make up the urban agglomerations. The following are the important definitions according to Census of India, 2011 (Kumar, et al., 2021):

Statutory Towns: "Settlements that are notified under law by the concerned State/UT government and with local bodies such as municipal corporations, municipalities, municipal committees, etc., irrespective of their demographic characteristics" (Kumar, et al., 2021).

Census Town: "Settlements that are classified as urban in the census after they have met the following criteria: a minimum population of 5,000, at least 75% of the male 'main workers' engaged in non-agricultural pursuits, and a density of population of at least 400 persons per sq. km. These are governed as villages and do not necessarily have urban local bodies" (Kumar, et al., 2021).

Outgrowths: "These are viable units, such as a village, clearly identifiable in terms of their boundaries and locations. Outgrowths possess urban features in terms of infrastructure and amenities, such as pucca roads, electricity, etc., and are physically contiguous with the core town of the urban agglomeration" (Kumar, et al., 2021).

Figure 2.3: Composition of Urban Population in India - figure shows how urban population is divided in 3 major parts.

Source: <https://www.niti.gov.in/sites/default/files/2021-09/UrbanPlanningCapacity-in-India-16092021.pdf>

Urban Planning System

The development of rural India, based on Gandhian principles and urban planning in India was not given much attention until the 1960s and 1970s (Jain & Pallagst, 2015). Planning often takes the shape of economic planning in India. A lack of spatial planning is seen at the highest levels of the planning system (Jain & Pallagst, 2015). According to Swamy et al. (2007); Kundu (2011) and WB(2013) as cited by Jain & Pallagst (2015), although the division of responsibilities is appropriate, spatial planning has proven ineffective and is marked by regional disparities due to its initiation at the regional or municipal level.

In India, planning majorly consists only of recommendations rather than execution. For instance, both the national and state governments in India are in charge of planning. It is not subject to any legislative enactment's force in Mathur's (1978) opinion as cited by Jain & Pallagst (2015). The Town and Country Planning Office (TCPO), which operates at the national level, issues policies that direct planning (Jain & Pallagst, 2015).

The separate responsibilities and power assigned to the local authorities by the state governments (Jain & Pallagst, 2015). The 74th Constitution Amendment Act (CAA) of 1992, which advocated for decentralization, proposed the establishment of a Metropolitan Planning Committee (MPC) and a District Planning Committee (DPC), gave urban local bodies (i.e., municipalities) constitutional status, and strengthened the financial authority of these entities, allowing them to function as effective and prospering democratic self-government units according to Mathur (2009) and PC (2013) cited by (Jain & Pallagst, 2015).

For vast regions that encompass both rural and urban areas, the DPC and MPC must coordinate the plans from the municipality and panchayat at the district and metropolitan levels. However, the MPC and the DPC are dysfunctional in the majority of states (Jain & Pallagst, 2015).

(Dysfunctional - This means that the Municipal Planning Committees (MPC) and District Planning Committees (DPC) are not functioning effectively in most states in India. They may not be carrying out their roles and responsibilities as intended, which could lead to issues in the planning and development of cities and districts within those states. As a result, the planning process and decision-making regarding urban and district development may be inefficient or not happening at all in many areas of the country.)

Figure 2.4: Indian Urban Planning System.

Source: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/254334501_The_Ahmedabad_Urban_Development_Plan-making_Process_A_Critical_Review

A fundamental transition from a Top Down Approach to a Bottom Up Approach, wherein decision-making is to take place at the local level, was made with the passage of the 74th Constitutional Amendment Act, 1992 (Jain & Pallagst, 2015). Nagar Panchayats (for areas in transition from rural to urban), Municipal Councils (for smaller urban areas), and Municipal Corporations (for larger urban areas) have been given the authority to act as plan-making and plan-implementation entities (Jain & Pallagst, 2015). Additionally, it has a clause governing the establishment of Metropolitan Planning Committees (MPC) and District Planning Committees (DPC). In order to create a development plan for the whole district, the DPC must combine the plans created by the Panchayats and Municipalities in the district (Jain & Pallagst, 2015). MPC is in charge of creating an overall Metropolitan region Draft Development Plan.

According to the Indian Constitution, there are two types of local self-governments: municipalities for urban regions and “Gram Panchayats” for rural areas. While the municipalities are in charge of delivering infrastructure, urban and town planning, planning for economic and social growth, and controlling land use, the Gram Panchayat is in charge of promoting economic growth and social justice, according to the Government of India 2007 report (Jain & Pallagst, 2015). The pace of expansion has made it difficult for the local authority to accommodate and control growth.

Statutory Towns Growing Without ‘Master Plans’

Master plans play an important role in managing urbanization, which are designed to govern and in command land use over the next 20–25 years, including growth and zoning of cities (Kumar, et al., 2021). Approximately half of India’s statutory towns do not have a master plan for their future expansions, according to statistics published by TCPO (Town and Country Planning Organization) (Kumar, et al., 2021). Numerous challenges are regularly mentioned, such as delays and legal problems, are encountered during the execution of master plans. Additionally, some master plans undergo over a thousand revisions while being put into practice (Kumar, et al., 2021). There might be a variety of causes for this. For instance, there are several departments and development authorities that are not in touch with one another, and development policies have not been communicated with residents. At times, it is claimed that master plans lack a comprehensive approach to address funding challenges, resulting in fragmented interventions, disorderly city growth, inefficient utilization of urban space, and urban sprawl (Kumar, et al., 2021).

Scales of Physical Interventions in Cities

The scale of physical interventions in cities refers to the different levels at which planning and development decisions are made. Here’s an explanation of each level:

	<p>1. National/State level policy making</p> <p>At the National or State level, planning skills are pertinent for policy formulation, vision preparation, programme design, strategic positioning of projects etc.</p> <p>At the highest scale, there are national-level policies formulated by the central government of the country or state-level policies formulated by the respective state governments. These policies provide broad guidelines and frameworks for urban development across the entire nation or state. They set out the overall vision, goals, and principles to be followed in urban planning and development.</p>
	<p>2. Regional plans</p> <p>The regional plan covers a larger area than individual cities but smaller than the entire state. It focuses on the development and coordination of multiple cities and towns within a specific region. Regional plans address issues that extend beyond the boundaries of a single city, such as transportation, infrastructure, environmental concerns, and overall growth patterns for the region.</p> <p>Regional plans address the multi sectoral aspects and give direction and priorities for investments and development. Preparation, implementation, and review of regional plans is a cyclic process. Planning skills are predominantly applicable here for devising a bigger picture and a strategy while encompassing considerations about multiple sectors like transportation, tourism, agriculture, land, industries, forests, environment and so on.</p>

Figure 2.5: Urban Planning at different scale in India: Hierarchy of Plans.

Source: Author’s own illustrations

	<p>3. Master plans</p> <p>The master plan is prepared for individual cities or urban areas. It outlines the development strategy and land use policies for that particular city. The master plan takes into account the regional plan and aligns the city's goals and objectives with the broader regional vision. It specifies the allocation of land for various purposes, such as residential areas, commercial zones, industrial areas, parks, and infrastructure development.</p> <p>The city master plans or development plans are statutory in nature. They define land uses and a set of norms to which all the constructions in the city must comply with. Their preparation, implementation and review entail a cyclic process which needs planning skills (both technical as well as managerial) for moderation, consensus building, and decision making with a team of multi-disciplinary experts (which may include architects, civil engineers, data scientists, transportation planners, environmental planners and so on.) Other city scale plans that need specialist expertise of planners include city sanitation plans, comprehensive mobility plans and so on.</p>
	<p>4. Local area level planning, building level interventions</p> <p>At the most granular level, there are local-level area plans or building plans. These plans focus on specific neighborhoods, sectors, or zones within the city. They provide detailed guidelines and regulations for construction, land use, and development within these smaller areas. Building plans may also specify the height, density, setbacks, and other parameters for individual structures.</p> <p>This scale of intervention predominantly needs urban design, architecture and engineering skills. Depending on the nature of the area being planned, such as a transit-oriented zone planning, may also need specialist skills such as Transportation planning, environmental planning and so on. At the building level, the role of a planner is mainly in terms of permits and compliances.</p>

Figure 2.6: Urban Planning at different scale in India: Hierarchy of Plans - starting from city level plans to individual plot level development .

Source: Author's own illustrations

Overall, this hierarchy of planning helps in ensuring that development occurs in a coordinated and organized manner, considering both the broader regional context and the specific needs of individual cities and local areas. It allows for efficient allocation of resources, infrastructure, and services to create sustainable and well-designed urban spaces.

Microlevel Planning in India

A macro-level plan (development plan or master plan) spanning across the city and its surroundings is used to carry out development in the cities. The time between revisions may differ from state to state, although it typically lasts for roughly 10 years (Adhvaryu, 2023). This plan outlines the development's course of action in accordance with the existing town planning regulations. For land-use zoning, the plan specifies 'broad-brush' maps which are used to specify purposes including residential, commercial, and industrial

(Adhvaryu, 2023). The height and mass of buildings, as well as the site coverage (or margins), are all governed by development control regulations (Adhvaryu, 2023). The prospective urban road network, along with the intended arrangement and overall widths of the roads (right-of-way), are described on the transportation side (Adhvaryu, 2023). The plan also specifies upgrades to underground utilities including drainage, sewage, and water supply, as well as other public facilities (Adhvaryu, 2023). If appropriate, other special interest areas, such as tourist development and environmental and historical protection, may also be included.

There are two methods for controlling new growth at the subsequent level of planning following the macro-level plan. In one strategy, planning authorities purchase agricultural property from the owners in large numbers on current market value and re-plan them appropriately (Gopinath, 2010). The 'land acquisition' method is the name given to this strategy. In the second strategy, known as the "land readjustment and pooling" approach, rather than buying land from individual owners, land is has been pooled and then development takes place. In this method the transformation take place in such a way that delivers uniform forms of the initial plots and utilizes a portion of the land for basic infrastructure (Gopinath, 2010). The second way has the major benefits of avoiding displacing the original owners and, more crucially, giving the owners a share of the increase in land value whenever the property is sold and put to use for urban purposes (Jain, 2019). In addition, compared to the land acquisition approach, the government's facilitative role makes it less likely to be subject to corrupt activities according to Gopinath (2010) as cited by (Ballaney, 2008).

A Brief Introduction to Town Planning Scheme (TP Scheme) Process

The DP area (Development Plan Area) is subdivided into multiple town planning schemes, each encompassing approximately 100 hectares (Adhvaryu, 2023). For areas about 100 hectares, detailed town planning schemes are often created with the goal of "converting previous agricultural plots into urban plots with appropriate shape, size, and access"(Gopinath, 2010). The fundamental idea behind the TP Scheme is to consolidate all the land, usually spanning between 100 and 200 hectares, currently owned by different individuals or entities. This land is then redistributed in a properly reconfigured layout, which includes allocating space for recreational areas, social facilities, services, homes for the economically weaker section,

and the road network (Gopinath, 2010). In this approach, a group of landowners is temporarily brought together by a local planning agency or development authority for planning purposes under the auspices of the state-level town or urban planning statute (Adhvaryu, 2023). The development authority has positive influence over the layout and development of the peri-urban region thanks to this method, which also allows it to develop land without entirely possessing it (Adhvaryu, 2023).

Figure 2.7: Connections between Development Plan and Town Planning Scheme in India.

Source: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/254334501_The_Ahmedabad_Urban_Development_Plan-making_Process_A_Critical_Review

The nationwide Building Code (NBC), which provides a nationwide framework for "development control" (Jain, 2019). In order to get a "development permit" (such as, for any material change on the use of land, such as the subdivision of land into residential plots) or "building permits"; General Development Control Regulations (Building Bye-Laws and Municipality Building Rules) need to be met. At two different levels these requirements should be met: (1) the zonal level, where the proposed development has to follow the criteria as per the Master Plan or the Detailed Town Planning Scheme; and (2) the building/plot level, where development has to follow different specifications as mentioned in the GDCR or (such as the minimum size of a habitable room or the minimum width of a corridor) (Gopinath, 2010).

In India, development control depends on zoning regulations and building by-laws (Gopinath, 2010). The urban development authority, which is made up of state governments, and local governments are the two main actors within "development control" (Gopinath, 2010). Every individual who plans to carry out development must get a "development permission" to guarantee that upcoming development align with development control regulation and the Master Plan: If development comes under the local government's jurisdiction, it must come from the local government; if development is outside the local government's jurisdiction but still within its boundaries, it must come from the concerned urban development authority (Gopinath, 2010).

A Gap in the Process

Various literature sources provide an understanding of the current practices of urban planning in India. The literature highlights that urban planning is often carried out at the city level, where development plans are formulated to guide the overall growth and infrastructure of the urban area. Additionally, specific regulations, known as development control regulations, are implemented at the individual property level to ensure compliance with zoning and construction guidelines.

However, upon analyzing the literature, an intriguing observation emerges – there exists an untapped potential to connect and integrate the city-level planning with individual property-level regulations. This integration could pave the way for the introduction of urban design qualities that go beyond mere functional aspects and contribute to enhancing the overall quality of life for the residents. This scenario emphasizes the need for a paradigm change towards masterplan-led development, in which the focus expands beyond single-plot issues to include a holistic strategy that provides multidimensional advantages.

By incorporating urban design features, such as well-planned public spaces, pedestrian-friendly walkways, green landscapes, and aesthetically pleasing architecture, cities can foster a more attractive and livable environment. A well-designed urban setting has the potential to positively impact the overall well-being of its residents, promoting physical and mental health, social interaction, and a sense of community. Creating livable communities requires more than just social and environmental benefits; it also necessitates ensuring economic viability. A balanced approach that considers economic sustainability alongside social and environmental aspects is essential to build thriving and prosperous communities. Fundamentally, support for masterplan-led development is based on the awareness that such a strategy has the ability to produce significant environmental improvements while also catering to social and economic dynamics. Private developers and contractors, whose major focus is on maximizing economic profits, have a considerable effect on the contemporary perspective of urban development in India. A shift towards a master plan oriented strategy, on the other hand, brings a transformational viewpoint that aligns the pursuit of economic benefits with the larger context of social well-being.

Moreover, literature highlights that the integration of urban design principles into the city-level planning and individual property-level regulations has the potential to enhance the value of properties within the urban area. Homes and commercial spaces that are part of well-designed neighborhoods with appealing surroundings tend to command higher property values, attracting potential buyers and investors.

This research project aims to support the hypothesis that masterplan-led development produces better economic outcomes than a sole concentration on individual plot-level endeavors. The research intends to reveal the hidden potential of masterplan-led initiatives in delivering long-term economic gains by digging into analysis. In essence, this study aims to demonstrate how masterplan-led development techniques may comprehensively integrate private interests within a framework that leads to a more complete and sustainable urban development environment.

In conclusion, by connecting city-level planning with property-level regulations and introducing urban design masterplan for site specific development, cities can create more vibrant, functional, and desirable urban environments that benefit residents and enhance property value. This study seeks to provide a persuasive argument for embracing masterplan-led solutions by emphasizing the numerous benefits such as environmental improvements, social cohesion, and economic growth. Furthermore, the research aims to show how such an approach might provide a realistic avenue for private developers and contractors to realize increased financial benefits while contributing to the general growth of the urban fabric. Next chapter explores how urban design qualities help to create more property values.

03

*Literature
Review*

Concept of Urban Design Quality

The definition of urban design is a subject of contradiction due to diverse perspectives among practitioners. This arises from the interdisciplinary nature of urban design influenced by various built environment professions. Three main themes emerge from this context.

1. **Ownership and Boundaries:** Different fields claim ownership of urban design, causing disputes over its boundaries. Greed (1998) highlights varying viewpoints from planners, architects, and landscape architects. Carmona (1998) explores these disparities, particularly between architecture and planning.

2. **Inclusive Perspective:** Urban design seeks to bridge gaps between architecture and planning. This approach, reflected in contemporary theories by Lang (2005) and Cuthbert (2007), arose from city fragmentation following the separation of architecture and planning professions.

3. **Connecting Professions:** Carmona et al. (2008) position urban design as connecting diverse professions, yet debates persist over its intermediary or independent role (Cuthbert, 2007). Urban design is seen as a process and outcome, emphasizing their relationship (Madanipour, 1997).

Recent trends highlight urban design's role in enhancing cities' global competitiveness (Madanipour, 2006). It stems from paradigms in architecture and planning, dating back to the early 20th century City Beautiful Movement. Modern urban design addresses new imperatives, emphasizing quality environments and risk reduction (Lang, 2005).

In conclusion, urban design's definition remains complex due to diverse perspectives. It spans processes and outcomes, growing in importance as a bridge between built environment fields, offering solutions in evolving global contexts.

Concept of Property Value

Defining value, much like urban design, remains complex due to varying perspectives. Value is often seen as a monetary exchange between buyers and sellers in a market. For the sake of this study

the built environment or real estate value. In real estate, two key value categories exist: “value in exchange” or market value, and “value in usage,” linked to worth and satisfaction.

The International Valuation Standards Council (IVSC, 2005) established a global understanding of value. Market value is the expected price when a property is fairly sold between willing parties after proper marketing (French, 2006). External forces shaping value include physical factors (climate, terrain), political factors (regulations, taxes), economic factors (employment, economy size), and social factors (demographics, living conditions).

The Appraisal Institute (1996) outlines four economic elements shaping value: utility, desire, effective buying power, and scarcity. Macmillan (2006) presents six value categories: exchange value (commercial worth), use value (productivity impact), image value (brand and identity), social value (community impact), environmental value (adaptability), and cultural value (symbolism).

The pursuit of pleasure and ease, as per Scitovsky’s method, separates value into personal and societal comfort (De Vries, 2008). Seeking pleasure brings specific experiences, while comfort involves relief from discomfort. Macmillan (2006) links social comfort to perceptions of self-image, contributing to value assessments.

In conclusion, value in the built environment is multifaceted, encompassing market and use value, influenced by diverse factors. Social and personal comfort contribute to how value is perceived, aiding in valuing high-quality urban design.

Utility, Urban Design Quality and Property Value

Property pricing aligns better with traditional urban design. The built environment, arising from urban planning and property development, benefits from this interdisciplinary approach (Madanipour, 1997; Tiesdell and Adams, 2011). The utility principle, rooted in consumer satisfaction, forms the basis. Utility theory explains how consumers select valued products. Kelvin Lancaster’s ideas are relevant, suggesting that utility arises from qualities. Rosen (1974) extended this to competing consumer durables, like real estate property. His concepts highlight the distinction of qualities and the market’s competitive nature.

Lancaster/Rosen technique assesses property value based on utilities or amenities, e.g., size, location, view taken into consideration. High-quality urban design enhances observable characteristics, increasing utility. Such products stand out by offering greater usefulness. Users seeking maximum utility opt for quality items, raising their comfort and utility. Social comfort boosts reputation, reinforcing utility maximization. Comparing quality product prices to average ones reveals market value or exchange value in the built environment. This discrepancy showcases the value of good urban design. Developers view it as higher returns tied to quality investment. This forms the basis for research on property attributes and pricing, particularly in property value assessment.

Figure 3.1: Utility Theory, Urban Design Theory and Property Value.

Source: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/epdf/10.1080/13574809.2015.1071657?needAccess=true&role=button>

Physical Characteristics of Property

Due to the crucial role physical characteristics play in home economics and the large money it provides for local governments, property value has long had a crucial place among planning researchers and practitioners. Two study streams have examined the degree to which external and internal connected design attributes have been associated with property values, according to a review of the body of literature on property values. The primary area of study in the first group focuses on the fundamental structural, aesthetic, and physical attributes of buildings. The second stream, on the other hand, places more emphasis on the built environment's aesthetic features as well as location amenities (such as proximity to shops, parks, and public transportation), emphasizing their importance to real estate prices.

Extensive research into the impact of physical factors on property values has identified various elements influencing property prices. For instance, factors like land size and building age play a role (Follain & Jimenez, 1885; Peiser, 1987). Moreover, property amenities, including the number of bedrooms, bathrooms, and pools, also contribute to price determination (Waddell, Bemy, & Hoch, 1993). Additionally, architectural significance and the quality of design and construction materials are crucial considerations (Hough & Kratz, 1983; Vandell & Lane, 1989). These factors are not confined to the US and also apply in the European property market. Several studies have revealed that greater premiums are necessary due to the high quality of design of building facades (Nase, et al., 2016).

Added Value of Quality in Real Estate Contxt

There has been a lot of study in the previous decade on the additional benefits of high-quality urban

design. Government agencies have been more interested in researching the benefits of outstanding design, particularly in terms of property values. They perform research to determine whether “good” urban design provides value. The concept of value-added implies that anything grows more useful as each component is improved. This means that improving the quality of every area of urban design leads to a more valued end product - the built environment.

Carmona et al.'s (2001) study shows that great design in urban environments has many benefits for different people. They discussed the advantages for various stakeholders briefly. The study found that smart design benefits almost everyone, but the reasons for valuing it may be linked to either private or public interests. These reasons can be short-term or long-term, depending on when the benefits are seen. Macmillan (2006) stresses the importance of understanding what stakeholders value to create an outstanding product. Carmona et al. (2001) also agree with this idea, stating that intelligent urban design provides benefits, whether short or long-term, to all stakeholders involved.

In 1989, Vandell and Lane were the first to explore how high-quality design relates to added value. They looked at 102 class A office buildings in Boston and Cambridge, comparing rent and vacancy rates. Their findings showed that good design affects both rent prices and vacancy rates. To analyze this, they used a hedonic model, which considered 10 different factors for a collection of class A commercial structures. A panel of specialists evaluated the overall design rating, considering eight aesthetically pleasing factors for newly built structures and three extra criteria for renovated buildings. The authors divided the data they collected into a five-scale quality gradient determined by the professionals they interviewed, and they discovered that structures with design quality ratings in the top 20% were expected to generate almost 22% more revenue from rentals than those with design quality ratings in the bottom 20%, demonstrating a significant impact of design on rents. A slight correlation between vacant space patterns and design quality was also discovered. Finally, Vandell and Lane (1989) came to the conclusion that “profitability is anticipated actually to go down on average with an improvement in design quality.”

Academic studies also primarily focus on how amenities affect home values. Internal housing quality factors like the number of bathrooms, the presence of a lift, and the building's quality were taken into account (Hoesli et al. 1997), as well as external environmental quality indicators like quietness, proximity to a view and a green space, accessibility to public transport, the quality of the neighborhood, and the location within the community. (Hoesli et al. 1997). Other scholars have concentrated on how the view, a single natural asset, affects home pricing. Benson et al. (1998) found that having a view can increase the value of a property by different percentages. For example, a partial beach view can add eight percent to the value, while an unobstructed beach view can increase it by sixty percent. The percentage varies depending on the type of view.

These findings represent a significant advancement since they show that design amenities may produce economic premiums. They also bring up the issue that certain architectural features—like the vicinity of a retail mall and a school in Geneva—may not necessarily carry the predicted financial benefits. In order to create an environmental quality index, in the greater Geneva region, Bender and his team (1997) studied eight hundred fifty houses for their research. This index can be described as an average of the quality parameters with values computed using the analysis of hierarchy methodology. The results indicate that, The distance to a green space and the serene atmosphere of the region are the most significant criteria among the seven environmental characteristics, which include peacefulness, availability to public transportation, closeness to downtown, attractive outlook, proximity to retail establishments, green areas, good schools, and social value. They have an 18% weight in terms of significance. The authors contend that this is acceptable for a relatively small town like Geneva. In contrast to nations like the US, respondents in Geneva place a lower value on educational institutions and shopping center proximity, according to Bender et al. (1997).

De Rosiers et al. (2002) investigation of 31 landscaping qualities shows that various landscape elements have an effect on particular types of single-family dwellings (bungalows, cottages, and row homes), which provides supporting evidence for this particular issue. The authors hypothesized when an increased tree cover difference between a property and its adjacent neighborhood translates into a greater home value, an above-average vegetation density visible from the premises has a negative influence on pricing. Additionally, in the case of villas and cottages, a large proportion of ground cover (grass, flowerbeds, rock plants, etc.) often demand a premium on the market. Additionally, elements like a fence, a planted patio, and landscaping was created to help significantly boost a property's value.

By examining facilities at the neighborhood level, research on the value provided by great design is moving closer to the urban scale. This research draws inspiration from the New Urbanism movement and its principles, which center on shaping the construction of cities. In order to demonstrate how design affects value-added assessments, research, which is based primarily in the US, has begun to incorporate certain fundamental principles of urban design quality (such as the setting, accessibility, mix of uses, sustainability, and connectivity).

Users' preferences for neo-traditional neighborhoods were examined by Morrow-Jones et al. in 2004. They polled customers on their choices for neo-traditional township design elements including layout, housing density, nearby open space, and commute time while holding pricing and other design elements constant. According to their research, suburban single-family, low-density projects are favored over New Urbanist design elements focused on increasing density. New Urbanist design elements, however, appear to be following up in the market. Song and Quercia (2008), who first categorized the urban built settings into several neighborhood types and discovered that various customer requirements are related to each stratum, provide additional support for these findings. More specifically, in traditional and neo-traditional communities, it was stated that traditional design elements like higher density, improved street connectivity, and easy access to shops contribute to increased property value in urban areas. In contrast, it was noted that in suburban neighborhoods, higher property value is associated with lower dwelling density and a more uniform land use pattern.

Important ideas of quality in home selection have also been introduced according to New Urbanism design principles. According to reports, internal connectivity and urban surroundings attract high prices. According to research, urban design strongly influences value, with infill designs fetching a premium that is larger than that of enclave and traditional neighborhood development (TND). In simple terms, the higher the value of housing to the end user, the more closely it may be connected to its setting. (Weber and Ryan 2005).

In the Portland metropolitan area region, Song and Knaap (2003) identified certain design elements of the New Urbanist movement. The key conclusion was that elements of New Urbanist architecture raised home values by 15.5%. Another crucial discovery was that features categorized under internal connectivity, (like interconnected street networks, more sidewalks, fewer dead ends, smaller blocks, and proximity to the subway) had positive effects on house prices. On the other hand, features grouped under external connectivity had different effects. (such as neighborhoods with high density and comprise more public, multifamily, and commercial uses relative to single-family uses and contain major transportation arterials) had a negative impact on value. According to the research analysis mentioned above, various kinds of urban built environments have varied pricing for neighborhood design qualities. Demand factors are responsible for this variation in neighborhood characteristics and pricing across submarkets (Song and Querca 2008).

Recent academic studies on the (economic) value supplied by high-quality design have emphasized sustainability. In studies on buildings with green labels, it was found that the value of such structures can be significantly increased by eco-friendly design. The information obtained was considered surprising (Eichholtz et al. (2010) and Wiley et al. (2010)). Premiums for class A corporate buildings with green designs were discovered to differ significantly. Even if rents have increased by 7–17%, according to Wiley et al. (2010) the selling premium might reach \$129 per square foot. Occupancies have also increased by 10–18%. A commercial building's environmental certification would result in a 2% rise in rentals per square foot and an addition of 16% to the selling price, according to similar results made by Eichholtz et al. (2010). Eco design, however still in its infancy, strongly implies that sustainability principles are beneficial.

A significant body of research on urban design attributes reveals that streets with easy access to shopping, lots of green space, and a diversity of land uses have an impact on property prices. The evidence suggests there may be a high demand for neighborhoods that are walkable in both residential and non-residential areas, although this may depend in part on the socioeconomic profile of a neighborhood (e.g., income, level of education) (Diao & Ferreira (2010), Gilderbloom et al. (2015), Pivo & Fisher (2011)). A recent study across the US looked at how easy it is to walk in different areas and how it affects property value. They analyzed 4237 office, apartment, retail, and industrial properties from 2001 to 2008. The results showed that improving walkability by 10% could increase property values by 1% to 9%, depending on the type of property. This study used Walk Score to measure walkability (Pivo & Fisher, 2011). In the Boston metropolitan region, similar research by Diao and Ferreria (2010) found that if the walkability score improves, property prices could go up by 1.42%. or \$5340 for a house valued at \$376,500.

Street design also frequently correlates with property prices according to several studies done by Asabere (1990), Guttery (2002), Matthews & Turnbull (2007), Song & Knaap (2003). According to one research by Matthews and Turnbull (2007), grid street designs have a significant impact on customers and are positively correlated with greater property prices, especially in communities that cater to pedestrians. Greater accessibility, street connection, and diverse land uses are factors that contribute to higher property prices in this situation, as shown by neo-traditionalist communities (Koster & Rouwendal, 2012).

According to studies, properties near local amenities such as transportation systems, cultural artefacts, playgrounds, and recreational spaces are typically more valued. For instance, prior studies

have discovered that prices for houses located up to 16.4% closer to a transit station than those farther away can be found (Debrezion, et al., 2007). The average single-family house premium in transit-adjacent regions was 2.3% more than in areas without access to transit, according to a different research that used a metaanalysis (Hamidi et al., 2016). According to an empirical study done in Sweden's Jönköping region, open space in high density areas is a solid indicator of the urban housing market (Nilsson, 2014). Another geographic element is the vicinity to the Central Business District (CBD), which is often linked to greater property values (Colwell & Munneke, 1997, 1999).

In spite of the fact that architectural design is a matter of personal taste, research show that people are prepared to pay more for homes near famous examples of good architecture (Ahlfeldt & Mastro, 2012; Buitelaar & Schilder, 2017). Buitelaar and Schilder (2017) used a hedonic price model to analyze more than 60,000 transactions from 1995 to 2014 in a case study of the Dutch property market. Their research showed that older structures with neo-traditional influences demanded a 15% price premium.

However, practice research has had more success in resolving concerns like quality and value definition, in particular. The initial good design criteria were evaluated by RICS and DoE in 1996 and were divided into four categories: social and functional usage, sustainability and the natural world, visual appeal, and the urban environment. Property Council of Australia (1999) and Urban Task Force (1999) carried out comparable study, and by establishing quality standards, they laid the foundation for the policy framework that would govern later practice.

The main advantages of this initial phase of practice research are the effective attempts to establish the concept of quality that guides the regulatory structure to be used in subsequent practice. Research conducted during this time led to the idea that good places require excellent design, which is rooted in the ideas of designing for people, placemaking, environmental sustainability, and adaptability or endurance across time. Despite being widely accepted, research on the idea that good design provides value has received very little attention. The study supported by CABE and DETR, which adopted an integrated perspective and differentiate between three forms of value provided by good design, namely economic, social, and environmental, marked a clear advancement in this area. The research's consideration on mixed-use developments rather than single-use ones is its other most significant aspect (Carmona et al. 2001).

In terms of the value contributed by excellent design, the study substantially addressed gaps, particularly in seeking to distinguish between different forms of worth and blending the perspectives of all those who benefited from it. Additionally, it addressed the lack of public open space and the social component issue raised by Vandell and Lane (1989). This study asserts that "good design adds value" by qualitatively analyzing stakeholder interviews and scalability by the research team (Carmona et al. 2001).

The Ministry of Environment, New Zealand (MfE, 2005) came to the conclusion that urban design may be profitable, although usually over the course of the building's or place's existence instead of in the immediate future, and that frequently a well-designed urban area gives advantages outside of the site itself. The study described its key findings into five topics while acknowledging the challenges of measuring these advantages. First, although it initially costs more, smart urban design has a big impact on the neighborhood. Second, bad design may have detrimental implications on the economy, as well as the environment and social issues. Third, the community places a high priority on effective urban design that enhances quality of life. Fourth, by promoting activity, excellent urban design may have a positive impact on health. Fifth, effective urban design may significantly enhance a region's safety and security.

According to Savills (2007), "sustainable urbanism" refers to a set of predetermined characteristics in urban design, and it emphasizes the advantages of this design on all three fronts: economic,

social, and environmental. These studies show what makes an area more valuable in terms of economics. They talk about density, which means using land well to make more money over time. They also talk about capital, which means spending less on managing and maintaining things. Another thing they mention is mixed-use development, which means having different kinds of places like stores and offices so that the area can make money and create jobs. Finally, they talk about having well-designed spaces that look good and make the area more valuable (Carmona et al. 2001).

According to UK research (AMION et al. 2007), excellent urban design may create value by creating successful places, spaces, and structures. Assessing what defines urban design and determining the possible advantages of effective urban design are the goals of the study. Furthermore, it is responsible for providing a brief overview of the environmental impact assessment framework. Given that this is the first attempt to scale the link between urban design and property value frameworks, it ranks among the most current exercises (AMION et al. 2007).

Throughout the North West area, to develop the area for redevelopment of different types of projects. This assortment of case studies tries to show the framework's wide range of applications. According to the study's findings, smart urban design is associated with an increase in rental or capital value of up to 15-20%. Additionally, whole-life expenses can be decreased and lettings/sales prices can be hastened. Even while making investments in good design is financially possible, value is not always added. As value is location-related, it doesn't get added in the same way, and quality investments are typically more expensive (AMION et al. 2007).

Following chapter analyzes two case studies within London out of which one is masterplan led development and another is incremental growth. In order to analyze the difference between property price in two areas and see if masterplan led development influences the property value or not.

Parameters that Contributes to Quality of Urban Design

1. Accessibility to public transport
2. Proximity to CBD
3. Proximity to retail establishments
4. Proximity to Amenities
5. Proximity to a view
6. Proximity to green space
7. Playgrounds and Recreational spaces
8. Active Frontages
9. Interconnected street networks with Fewer dead ends
10. Improved sidewalks and walkability
11. Smaller blocks
12. Housing Mix

04

Case Studies

Two case studies have been taken into consideration, located in Newham borough of London. Two sites are Royal Wharf and Fishguardway.

Stratagic Location

Figure 4.1: Site Context - Site Location in London(Newham Borough of London).

Source: Google Earth Pro and Author's own illustrations.

Figure 4.2: Site Location in Newham Borough, London.

Source: Google Earth Pro and Author's own illustrations.

East London's Newham is an inner-city borough that is bordered by other metropolitan and suburban authorities and is only a few kilometers from the City. It borders the Thames to the south with a large area of historical docks, the River Lea to the west, and the River Roding to the east. In addition to the international and domestic air connections provided by London City Airport, strategically important road and rail connections connect it to the City of London to the west, the larger Thames Gateway region to the east of London, and the Stansted-Cambridge route to the north. Stratford is a particularly significant interchange with the potential for high-speed rail travel to Europe.

Both locations are in Newham's Royal Docks neighborhood. Royal Wharf was chosen as a case study to analyze masterplan-led development since the land has been designated for strategic development in the Newham local plan. Fishguard Way was analyzed to study incremental growth because the site had been developed as part of a local area plan.

Transportation and Connections

The DLR and Crossrail, which offer convenient access to Canary Wharf, central London, and the southeast of England, have benefitted The Royal Docks from major public investment. A future allocation for DLR station on the Woolwich branch is also currently planned. Connections on both the domestic and international levels are offered by London City Airport, along with related commercial prospects.

Custom House is the Crossrail station closest to Royal Wharf, and it offers feeder bus services as well as access for present and prospective Newham residents and companies. The Royal Wharf site's development maximizes the advantages of these nodes by connecting with Canning Town, supporting the river, bus, and bicycle networks, and promoting more use of the canal and riverbank through enhanced pedestrian connectivity and a potential expansion to the existing river bus services. King George's V is the Crossrail station closest to Fishguard Way, and it offers feeder bus services as well as access for present and prospective Newham residents and companies.

Figure 4.3: Transportation and Connections of Newham Borough, London.

Source: Digimap and Author's own illustrations.

Case Study 1: Royal Wharf

The Royal Wharf is located in the London Borough of Newham's (LBN) Royal Docks / Silvertown district. North Woolwich Road and Deanston Wharf are the site's northern and western boundaries, respectively. The Thames Barrier is located 100 meters to the east, and the River Thames marks the site's southern boundary. Around 17.23 hectares are occupied by the Royal Wharf property. There are no listed structures on the site or close by, and it is not situated in a conservation area. Thames Barrier Park, a sizable expanse of open space with parks and cultural institutions, situated to the west of the construction site.

The area was first built as an industrial complex towards the end of the 19th century, and it also served as a location for First World War industry. After that, Shell UK utilized the location as a storage and refinery facility for oil for a while. When the site was abandoned in the 1990s, this came to an end. Planning approval was given to redevelop the property with a mixed-use proposal in 2012 after extensive engagement with Newham Council staff, the Thames Gateway Corporation, and local community stakeholders (including local organizations and individual individuals).

New homes, including affordable housing for local people

A new primary school for local children

Hundreds of employment opportunities of varying skills and professions

A new high street of shops, restaurants and cafés

New leisure facilities including a new park

Significant contribution towards improving local health provisions, education, road networks and public transportation

Within the Royal Docks neighborhood of East London, Royal Wharf is a residential riverside development with more than 3,300 new houses, 10,000 square meters of commercial space, a school, and a community center. The development's open space makes up about half of the total area, and it includes residential gardens and courtyards, a centralized Market Square with benches, lawns, and planting, as well as Royal Wharf Gardens, a park with large expanses of seasonal vegetation surrounding a central lawn. Both locals and visitors can enjoy the playable and inclusive atmosphere provided by the terrain.

Construction on the site has been categorized into three stages, with Phase 1 starting in 2014. Royal Wharf

Gardens and Phase 1 were finished in 2016; Phases 2 and 3 were finished in 2019. Ballymore / Oxley International Holdings is the project's client, and Townshend Landscape Architects designed the masterplan.

Figure 4.5: Royal Wharf Location - Site Location in Newham Borough, London.

Source: Google Earth Pro and Author's own illustrations.

Figure 4.6: Royal Wharf, Newham Borough, London.

Source: Author's own photograph.

1. Accessibility to Public Transportation

A short distance away to the north-east and west, respectively from the site, are West Silvertown and Pontoon Dock Docklands Light Railway (DLR) and Bus Station, both of which are along North Woolwich Road. Two bus stations are also strategically placed within a distance of around 100 meters from the location. The location also offers a wide range of connectivity, made possible by six bus stops, two well-known tube stations, and a riverboat service. This well-organized transport system guarantees that the location is easily accessible from different areas of the city. According to a survey of the literature, a property's value is significantly impacted by its closeness to transit.

Figure 4.7: (top) Royal Wharf - Accessibility to Public Transportation.

Source: Digimap and Author's own illustrations.

Figure 4.8: (bottom) Pontoon DLR (Dock Dockland Light Rail) Station.

Source: Author's own photograph

2. Proximity to CBD

The advantageous aspect of close proximity to the Central Business District (CBD) is a pivotal determinant in property value, owing to its facilitation of convenient access to a multitude of employment opportunities. In this context, the site's strategic positioning a mere few miles away from the CBD is accentuated by the presence of robust transportation links, effectively streamlining the commuting process to and from the CBD. This symbiotic relationship between the site's geographic location and the efficiency of transportation networks renders the daily commute to the CBD a seamless and expedient experience. The confluence of favorable geographic positioning and well-established transportation links serves to alleviate potential commuting challenges, thereby enhancing the site's allure for potential residents and property buyers. This amalgamation not only elevates the site's intrinsic value by virtue of its proximity to significant economic hubs but also underscores the practicality and convenience of its location, imbuing it with an added layer of desirability.

3. Proximity to Retail Establishments

The site benefits from its proximity to various key retail centers including Custom House, a neighborhood shopping center, as well as the district centers of Canning Town and Beckton, all of which are situated in close proximity. Notably, the local planning initiatives for Newham have included the development of a new town center within the Royal Wharf area. This strategic inclusion is integral to the broader urban development approach. Notably, recent studies have consistently indicated that the proximity to these retail and commercial hubs has garnered substantial interest from property buyers. This factor, in turn, has wielded a discernible influence on the valuation of properties within the vicinity. This confluence of accessible amenities and the strategic creation of a new town center underscores the significance of urban planning decisions in shaping property values and enhancing the overall desirability of the area.

Figure 4.9: Royal Wharf - Proximity to Retail Establishments - map shows the proximity to the local, district and major retail centers from the site.

Source: Google Earth Pro and Author's own illustrations.

Figure 4.10: Royal Wharf - New Local Shopping Center - photo shows the high street located in the Royal Wharf.

Source: Author's own photograph

4. Proximity to Amenities

Figure 4.11: Royal Wharf - Proximity to Amenities.

Source: Google Earth Pro and Author's own illustrations.

Figure 4.12: Royal Wharf - Primary School.

Source: Author's own photograph

The inclusion of a High Street within the development plays a pivotal role in drawing numerous local businesses to the area. This dynamic blend of commercial enterprises adds vibrancy and economic vitality to the site. Furthermore, the integration of essential amenities such as schools and a community center has significantly contributed to fostering a mixed-use development. This strategic approach aligns with contemporary urban design principles that prioritize the coexistence of residential, commercial, and communal spaces within a single locale.

Existing scholarly literature substantiates the notion that mixed-use developments, coupled with convenient access to amenities, exert a substantial pull factor on potential property purchasers. This gravitational effect translates into a willingness to invest higher monetary values in properties situated within such contexts. The amalgamation of diverse functionalities not only augments the appeal of the development to a wider demographic but also engenders an environment characterized by convenience and a sense of community.

In essence, the High Street's role as a hub for local businesses enriches the fabric of the development by fostering economic exchanges and nurturing a vibrant urban atmosphere. Simultaneously, the integration of educational and communal facilities augments the concept of mixed-use development, thereby catering to modern lifestyles and preferences. These dynamics resonate strongly with the empirical findings from existing literature, affirming that the amalgamation of mixed-use elements and proximity to essential facilities tangibly influence property buyers to perceive higher worth in residential offerings within the development.

Figure 4.13: Royal Wharf - Community Center.
Source: Author's own photograph

Figure 4.15: Royal Wharf - High Street - Photo shows pedestrian priority area with mixed use development.
Source: Author's own photograph

Figure 4.16: Royal Wharf - High Street - Photo shows a Pharmacy located in Royal Wharf.
Source: Author's own photograph

Figure 4.17: Royal Wharf - High Street - photo shows retail on the ground floor and housing on the upper floors as a mixed use development.
Source: Author's own photograph

5. Proximity to View

The site offers unobstructed views of the river, and planned development has made sure that it protects the vista. To safeguard the views of the adjustment development, an additional 5 important viewing corridors have been created.

These are protected viewing corridors:

- 1 Views in from Britannia Village
- 2 View to the Pier
- 3 View to the River
- 4 View to the Thames Barrier
- 5 View to Canary Wharf

To maximize the view for each plot, perpendicular streets have been designed and linear development along the river side is avoided in the design.

Along with protected view corridors, visual links have been established to protect the viewing corridor. These visual links have greater connection to the major nodes like plazas and open spaces. The master plan's emphasis on ensuring river or green area views for every structure underscores its commitment to fostering an environment of aesthetic delight and natural connectivity. This design philosophy not only adds intrinsic value to the built environment but also resonates with the well-being of the inhabitants, enriching their daily living experiences. In amalgamating protected view corridors, purposeful visual links, and expansive vistas, the master plan manifests as a testament to urban design's potential to create harmonious, visually engaging, and inherently valuable living spaces. Many studies prove that properties with a view can fetch higher market value.

Figure 4.18: Royal Wharf - Proximity to View - Protected Views.
 Source: Google Earth Pro and Author's own illustrations.

Figure 4.19: Royal Wharf - Proximity to View - Visual Links and Nodes.
 Source: Google Earth Pro and Author's own illustrations.

Figure 4.20: Royal Wharf - View Across the River.

Source: Author's own photograph

Figure 4.21: Royal Wharf - View to the Canary Wharf.

Source: Author's own photograph

Figure 4.22: Royal Wharf - Protected View to the River.
Source: Author's own photograph

Figure 4.23: Royal Wharf - Main Focal Point - MarketSquare.
Source: Author's own photograph

6. Proximity to Green Spaces

Site has close proximity to 3 major metropolitan parks, one district park and 2 local parks. Along with these parks and green spaces the site also comprises a variety of green spaces. A number of families of garden typologies, kitchen gardens, and public spaces with various personalities, identities, and roles are established throughout the masterplan in addition to creating a distinct hierarchy of streetscapes. As part of the landscape masterplan, a number of initiatives were developed to strengthen the design concepts. The hard landscape and street furniture palettes, which clearly delineate locations while producing a readable public realm with a recognisable hierarchy, represent the creation of a distinct neighborhood for modern London. The ideas were implemented by creating pedestrian-friendly streets, routes, and places employing

The concepts were executed through the design of walkable streets, pathways, and spaces, as well as the use of site-wide material palettes and methodologies to define the character and character variations within the site.

Royal Wharf Gardens

In order to give containment and opportunity to engage in active and passive leisure and play, the park is composed of a sizable expanse of sculpted lawn that is bordered by trees and vegetation with year-round appeal. There are several openings that activate the edges, and restrict vehicle access. The plants and landforms are intended to reduce any possible severe riverside winds. A swale at the eastern end of the park is used to route water runoff from the land to the river via tidal terraces. Under the tree canopies, native planting is divided into playable areas by boardwalk bridges and stepping stones. In close proximity, a retention pond or depression in the landform permits runoff to flow back to the land. A historical war memorial was recently established in the park.

The ‘Garden Courtyard’

The ‘Garden’ courtyards provide local areas for the residents of the properties around each garden court, adding to the site’s amenities. The gardens were designed as a collection of exclusive areas that were only open to the occupants of the nearby buildings. The development’s overall aim is to create a neighborhood that reacts to dwelling types, streets, and places that have a recognisable palette, hierarchy, and purpose. This is done by modernizing classic residential districts in London. The designs are inspired by London’s garden squares, where it is customary to designate open areas for both public and private ‘key holder’ gardens. These squares have a similar scale and design and include features like lawns, mounds, seating areas, focal points, and play areas in addition to plantings of trees, shrubs, and herbaceous plants. The goal is to establish a “family” of gardens, each with a unique design but united by a common character that will support Royal Wharf’s status as a distinctive area. According to research, homes that are close to green space tend to have higher property values than other homes.

Figure 4.24: Royal Wharf - Proximity to Green Space - Local, District and Metropolitan Parks.
 Source: Google Earth Pro and Author's own illustrations.

Figure 4.25: Thames Barrier Park - Nearby Local Park from Royal Wharf.
 Source: Author's own photograph

Figure 4.26: Royal Wharf - Proximity to Green Space within the Royal Wharf.
 Source: Google Earth Pro and Author's own illustrations.

Figure 4.27: Royal Wharf - Gateway - Linear park along the North Woolwich main road.
 Source: Author's own photograph

Figure 4.28: Royal Wharf - Riverside Walk.
Source: Author's own photograph

Figure 4.29: Royal Wharf - Semi Private Space.
Source: Author's own photograph

7. Playgrounds and Recreational spaces

The Royal Wharf concept includes illustrations of the primary public realm and urban places. A crucial element of the Royal Wharf project is the environment and public realm. The master plan's objective is to develop a new, exciting neighborhood in London that will house families and sustain a new population. This will be strengthened by how the public space is constructed. The masterplan's market plaza and Royal Wharf Park have been included in the defined hierarchy of streetscapes and unique spaces that has been established for the public realm. The courtyards provide local areas for the inhabitants of the buildings around each garden court, adding to the site's amenities. The Thames Clipper service to the south is reached by walkers and bikes at Silvertown Pocket Square, a prominent urban area. The square is one of a series of areas that lead to the Thames Clipper. According to research, homes that are close to playgrounds and other recreational areas might command higher property prices than other homes.

Figure 4.30 Royal Wharf - Playgrounds and Recreational Spaces within the Royal Wharf.
 Source: Google Earth Pro and Author's own illustrations.

Figure 4.31: Royal Wharf - Thames Barrier Park Square.
 Source: Author's own photograph

Figure 4.32: Royal Wharf - Linear Park.
Source: Author's own photograph

Figure 4.33: Royal Wharf - Market Square.
Source: Author's own photograph

Figure 4.34: Royal Wharf - Silvertown Pier Square.
Source: Author's own photograph

Figure 4.35: Royal Wharf - Silvertown Pocket Square.
Source: Author's own photograph

Figure 4.36: Royal Wharf - Active Frontages of the Buildings.
 Source: Google Earth Pro and Author's own illustrations.

Figure 4.36: Royal Wharf - Active Building Frontage near Market Square - photo shows vibrant public realm by creating active building edges.
 Source: Author's own photograph

8. Active Frontage

The viability of the plots depends on the frontages that are built. The strategy seeks to strategically construct areas with a variety of distinct building frontages to add character and variation across every street and the neighborhood as a whole. In accordance with the master design, buildings were to have extensive lengths of facade that were divided into principal and subsidiary orders and had a distinct hierarchy at the elevation. However, it is anticipated that each plot's use may be deduced from its façade, which will articulate the facade and define the building character into the street, regardless of how the plot land use is determined by the masterplan strategic parameters. Building frontages that are active draw greater attention to the street and the public realm, increasing investment potential.

9. Interconnected Street Network

North Woolwich road acts as a primary access road to the site. Two major primary vehicular access points have been created from the major transportation link North Woolwich road. To connect primary roads with other parts of the site secondary and tertiary vehicular movement links are established. In order to enhance the walkability in specific areas, restricted access or pedestrian priority streets have been designed. An interconnected roadway network with fewer dead ends helps to produce higher property value, as shown by the interconnectedness and hierarchy of the literature review section.

10. Improved Sidewalks and Walkability

Across the river and along the high street a major primary pedestrian street has been designed which has direct connections to the secondary connectors. Secondary connectors have then led people towards access points of the buildings. A well established pedestrian network encourages property buyers to make an investment as it provides a vibrant public realm which boosts property value.

The hierarchy of streets seeks to provide the development of a sense of normalcy by using a dialect that is common to London. The materials specification was created in accordance with Newham's requirements that can be adopted. This hierarchy guides the design strategy for the "High Street," lanes, and mews streets by guiding the layout, size, and materials.

High Street

Through the heart of Royal Wharf, the High Street acts as a crucial spine. The pathway pavement is marked with Yorkstone, a typical London paving material. To establish a clean zone along building frontages that allows for unobstructed access and pedestrian circulation, loading bays, street furniture, lighting and seats have been placed beside the kerb.

Street and Lanes

The streets and lanes have traditional concrete pavements to contrast with the High Street and reinforce the site hierarchy.

Mews

A cobbled mews vibe is created by a variety of settings. This coordinates with the parking spaces, loading docks, and elevated pedestrian overpasses. The idea is to create a feeling of location while also visually connecting the mews to features in the streets and alleys.

Figure 4.38: Royal Wharf- Interconnected Street Network - map shows Primary, Secondary and tertiary routes for vehicular movement.

Source: Google Earth Pro and Author's own illustrations.

Figure 4.39: Royal Wharf - Pedestrian Movement Network - map shows Primary, Secondary and tertiary routes for pedestrian movement.

Source: Google Earth Pro and Author's own illustrations.

Riverwalk Development

The Riverside Walk, which extends more than 500 meters along the site's south side, offers recreational opportunities for both locals and visitors while also providing views of Canary Wharf, the Millennium Dome, and the Thames Barrier. The landscaping is designed to mimic the swaths of native riverside bed reeds that along the entire course of the park. In order to cater to a range of users, seats, small-scale play areas, and outdoor exercise equipment have been added at various points along the path.

Figure 4.40: Royal Wharf - Hierarchy of Street.
 Source: Google Earth Pro and Author's own illustrations.

Figure 4.41: Royal Wharf - High Street (Primary Vehicular Movement with two lane road along with pedestrian walkways).
 Source: Author's own photograph

Figure 4.42: Royal Wharf - Secondary Vehicular Movement Street (with one lane and pedestrian walkways).
Source: Author's own photograph

Figure 4.43: Royal Wharf - Tertiary Vehicular Movement Street.
Source: Author's own photograph

Figure 4.44: Royal Wharf - Restricted Vehicular Movement Street.
Source: Author's own photograph

Figure 4.45: Royal Wharf - Restricted Vehicular Movement Street.
Source: Author's own photograph

Figure 4.46: Royal Wharf - Mews.
Source: Author's own photograph

Figure 4.47: Royal Wharf - Pedestrian Only Street (No Vehicular Movement Zone).
Source: Author's own photograph

11. Smaller Blocks

The master plan acknowledges the necessity to deconstruct urban blocks and boundaries within the framework of the block diagram in order to provide viable residential structures that are permeable and visually accessible. The graphic shows how the masterplan framework, as evaluated, enables this to grow within the scheme's overarching strategic objectives and context. To produce a smooth urban grain in layout and elevation and to prevent buildings from reading as big impermeable urban blocks in clustering or elevation treatment, all stages have been taken into consideration equally. For residents, a walking atmosphere is created through small, permeable urban blocks. According to studies, permeable and smaller blocks often have better property values.

12. Housing Mix

The graphic shows a house and flat layout for the project. The figure shows how dwellings within the framework of the masterplan may be constructed to connect with flats in addition to the mixed-use structures that have been suggested for the site. The housing has often been clustered around mews or home zone streets that are enclosed inside an ensemble of apartment buildings. By structuring the overall design in this way, each character region may generate a diverse range of dwelling typologies and tenures. The masterplan proposal specifies a defined residential unit mix for the complete masterplan site, comprising a variety of tenures, unit sizes, and typologies. According to studies, developments with a variety of dwelling types and uses tend to have greater property values.

Figure 4.48: Royal Wharf - Urban Blocks.
 Source: Google Earth Pro and Author's own illustrations.

Figure 4.49: Royal Wharf - Housing Typology.
 Source: Google Earth Pro and Author's own illustrations.

Figure 4.50: Royal Wharf - Apartments.
Source: Author's own photograph

Figure 4.51: Royal Wharf - Terrace Houses.
Source: Author's own photograph

Case Study 2: Fishguard Way

The Fishguard Way site is situated in the Royal Docks / Silvertown area of the London Borough of Newham (LBN). The site is bounded to the north by Albert Road and to the west Royal Victoria Garden. The River Thames forms the site's southern and eastern boundary of the site. The Fishguard Way site covers an area of approximately (5.14 hectares). The site is not located in a Conservation Area and there are no listed buildings on, or within close proximity to the site. To the west of the site is Thames Barrier Park which is a large area of open space containing parks and cultural facilities.

Figure 4.52: (top) Fishguard Way Location - Site Location in Newham Borough, London.

Source: Google Earth Pro and Author's own illustrations.

Figure 4.53: (bottom) Fishguard Way, Newham Borough, London.

Source: Author's own photograph

1. Accessibility to Public Transport

The closest Crossrail station from Fishguard Way is King George's V and is complemented with feeder bus services to provide access for current and future Newham residents and businesses. One bus stops in the vicinity of 100 meters of the site with no tube station. Six bus stops, 2 major tube stations and one riverboat service make the site connected with the rest of the city. Within 1500 meters around 11 bus stops and 3 tube stations are located near the site. Site does not have close proximity to the tube station which might negatively affect the property value. According to literature review, proximity to transportation has a significant impact on the property value.

2. Proximity to CBD

The advantageous aspect of close proximity to the Central Business District (CBD) is a pivotal determinant in property value, owing to its facilitation of convenient access to a multitude of employment opportunities. In this context, the site's strategic positioning a mere few miles away from the CBD is accentuated by the presence of robust transportation links, effectively streamlining the commuting process to and from the CBD. This symbiotic relationship between the site's geographic location and the efficiency of transportation networks renders the daily commute to the CBD a seamless and expedient experience. The confluence of favorable geographic positioning and well-established transportation links serves to alleviate potential commuting challenges, thereby enhancing the site's allure for potential residents and property buyers. This amalgamation not only elevates the site's intrinsic value by virtue of its proximity to significant economic hubs but also underscores the practicality and convenience of its location, imbuing it with an added layer of desirability.

Figure 4.54: Fishguard Way - Accessibility to Public Transportation.
 Source: Digimap and Author's own illustrations.

Figure 4.55: Fishguard Way - King George V DLR (Dock Dockland Light Rail) Station.
 Source: Author's own photograph

Figure 4.56: Fishguard Way - Proximity to Retail Establishments.
 Source: Google Earth Pro and Author's own illustrations.

Figure 4.57: Fishguard Way - Neighbourhood Retail Shops..
 Source: Author's own photograph

3. Proximity to Retail Establishments

The site in question enjoys a notable adjacency to the district centers, specifically Beckton. However, it is important to highlight that this site does not share a close proximity with any local town center. It is worth noting that a novel town center has been meticulously crafted in the vicinity of this site, an initiative aligned with the comprehensive local plan for Newham.

The significance of this geographical context is underscored by studies indicating that proximity to retail establishments tends to exert a favorable pull on prospective property buyers. This influence is notably reflected in property valuations. Given the current scenario, where the subject site lacks immediate access to a retail hub, there exists a plausible concern regarding the potential repercussions on its property value. The absence of a nearby retail center may indeed exert a negative impact on the perceived desirability and thus valuation of properties situated on this site.

4. Proximity to Amenities

Situated in close proximity to existing residential developments, the site's geographical location is noteworthy. However, an examination of the surrounding land use patterns reveals a prevalent concentration of residential development, which consequently poses challenges in terms of readily accessible amenities for the residents.

The effects of this lack of amenities go beyond simple convenience and might perhaps lower the value of real estate. The absence of conveniently located amenities places an additional burden on the residents, necessitating them to undertake additional efforts to fulfill their daily requirements. This inconvenience is not only time-consuming but also reflects a certain inconvenience that could be a significant factor in determining the desirability and ultimately the value of properties within the area.

In essence, the limited availability of adjacent facilities is a significant element that might have a detrimental impact on the site's total property value. The intrinsic difficulty brought on by the absence of close amenities, which forces people to make additional effort to meet their daily requirements, may unintentionally reduce the neighborhood's overall appeal to both potential buyers and inhabitants.

5. Proximity to a View

The site has uninterrupted river views. Development along the river side blocked the view for the adjoining area by developing continuous building blocks along the river. The development maximizes the river view which helps to generate higher property value. Viewing corridors have been provided to protect the views but compound wall interrupt the direct river view for the pedestrians, which act as a barrier. The development ensured that all the buildings either have a green space view or a river view. According to one study, partial or overall views of the natural features increase the property value.

Figure 4.58: (top) Fishquod Way - Proximity to View - Protected Views, Visual Links and Nodes.

Source: Google Earth Pro and Author's own illustrations.

Figure 4.59: (bottom) Fishquod Way - Protected View to the River.

Source: Author's own photograph

Figure 4.60: Fishguard Way - View Across the River
Source: Author's own photograph

Figure 4.61: Fishguard Way - Visual Link - Riverside Walkway (pedestrian cannot be able to see the river due t the barrier)
Source: Author's own photograph

Figure 4.62: Fishguard Way - Proximity to Green Space - Local, District and Metropolitan Parks.
 Source: Google Earth Pro and Author's own illustrations.

Figure 4.63: Fishguard Way - Nearby Local Park from Fishguard Way.
 Source: Author's own photograph

6. Proximity to Green Space

The site benefits from its convenient placement near a cluster of key metropolitan parks, including three main parks, a district park, and a local park. The development of the site itself included accommodations of green space. The harmonious blending of vegetation and natural areas plays a crucial part in determining the living environment. These green spaces help to make the neighborhood a welcoming and peaceful place to live. Such a large number of green areas promote serenity, accessibility to recreational possibilities, and an all-around greater quality of life.

Studies repeatedly demonstrate the significant effect of being close to green areas on property prices, highlighting the relevance of this characteristic. This agreement between the environment of the site and the available research supports the beneficial impact that these green spaces have on the appeal and therefore the value of houses nearby.

7. Playgrounds and Recreational Spaces

The Riverside Walk stands as a comprehensive recreational place. Its landscape design deliberately reflects the indigenous reed beds normally seen along river banks, with stretches of these natural vegetation generating a dynamic and continuous flow across the park's breadth. A noticeable observation throughout the path, however, indicates a noteworthy lack of sitting amenities at regular intervals, suggesting a probable failure to adequately provide comfort and relaxation for visitors. Although there are large open areas scattered throughout the route, they are all covered in an abundance of grass and trees and have no seats or play structures. This feature emphasizes an untapped potential to create varied leisure experiences that go beyond simple vegetation.

The inclusion of a public square together with sitting areas and river view results in a crucial improvement to the user experience. This clever addition establishes a welcoming environment that not only makes the most of the river vista but also promotes a sense of community and relaxation. The combination of these components helps to create an appealing social place for both locals and visitors. It is well acknowledged that having access to green spaces may increase home prices. It's important to keep in mind, too, that the Riverside Walk's lack of designated leisure places like playgrounds might possibly neutralize this beneficial effect. Lack of areas for active leisure may unintentionally result in a less lively and social environment, which may have an effect on the neighborhood's total property prices.

Figure 4.64: Fishguard Way - . Playgrounds and Recreational Spaces within the Fishguard Way.
 Source: Google Earth Pro and Author's own illustrations.

Figure 4.65: Fishguard Way - Main Public Space (with no entry point - only for esthetic purpose).
 Source: Author's own photograph

Figure 4.66: Fishguard Way - Public Plaza (with no benches or sitting places).
Source: Author's own photograph

Figure 4.67: Fishguard Way - Semi Private Spaces (with no benches or any additional sitting arrangement).
Source: Author's own photograph

8. Active Frontages

The site predominantly comprises residential development, distinctly focusing on providing residential units without integrating diverse land uses. The concept of active frontage contributes to a dynamic public environment; however, the absence of mixed-use elements might result in a less engaging communal space within the neighborhood. The implications of this could be either positive or negative for property values, as preferences differ among individuals. Some might favor a tranquil neighborhood characterized by serenity, while others may desire a vibrant atmosphere with active surroundings. The balance between quiet and active spaces plays a pivotal role in shaping the desirability and, consequently, the property value of the area.

9. Interconnected Street Network

Efforts to control vehicular traffic within the site are evident through a well-defined hierarchy for primary vehicular access originating from the main access road. This emphasis on primary access, restricted to the site's perimeters, underscores the intention to prioritize internal access for residents, categorized as secondary access and explicitly designed for their convenience rather than through traffic. A pivotal transition occurs where vehicular access is entirely prohibited, creating an exclusive pedestrian-only zone. This clear categorization of streets not only facilitates differentiation between various types of movement but also contributes to enhancing the overall functionality and aesthetic of the site. The presence of interconnected street networks, thoughtfully designed to accommodate different modes of movement, plays a pivotal role in cultivating an environment that inherently supports higher property values.

10. Improved Sidewalks and Walkability

A deliberate effort has been made to establish designated walkable pathways in close proximity to the riverside, aiming to foster a vibrant and accessible public space. These primary walkable routes serve as pivotal connectors, seamlessly linking to secondary and tertiary pedestrian routes, thus creating a hierarchical network of paths that cater to various levels of foot traffic. This hierarchical approach not only ensures efficient movement but also adds a layer of organization to the overall pedestrian experience. It's worth noting that enhancing walkability has been proven to exert a positive influence on property values, a correlation supported by extensive research findings. By prioritizing walkable routes near the riverside and structuring a comprehensive network of pathways, the development not only cultivates a desirable living environment but

also aligns with the potential for heightened property values in the area.

Figure 4.68: Fishguard Way - Interconnected Street Network.
Source: Google Earth Pro and Author's own illustrations.

Figure 4.69: Fishguard Way - Pedestrian Movement Network.
Source: Google Earth Pro and Author's own illustrations.

Figure 4.70: Fishguard Way - Main Access Road to the Site.
Source: Author's own photograph

Figure 4.71: Fishguard Way - Main Access Road to the Site.
Source: Author's own photograph

Figure 4.72: Fishguard Way - Primary Road - Restricted Vehicular Movement..
Source: Author's own photographs

Figure 4.73: Fishguard Way - Pedestrian Priority Road
Source: Author's own photograph

11. Smaller Blocks

The development strategically employs a block diagram to introduce permeability by breaking down traditional urban blocks and edges. This approach restricts vehicular access beyond specific points, fostering a pedestrian-friendly atmosphere. The design embraces smaller and more permeable urban blocks, resulting in an environment that encourages walkability among residents. Empirical studies consistently highlight the positive correlation between smaller block sizes and permeable layouts, and elevated property values. In this context, the deliberate emphasis on creating such an environment not only enhances the living experience but also aligns with the potential for increased property values.

12. Housing Mix

In the development there is only one typology of houses prevalent is apartment. Designing the development in this way restricts a rich mix of housing typologies and tenures to be developed within the area. The development application establishes a clear residential unit for one typology. As research defines that housing mix and mixed use development has higher property value development shows certain lack to fulfill this criteria.

Figure 4.73: FishguardWay - Urban Blocks.
Source: Google Earth Pro and Author's own illustrations.

Comparative Analysis

Parameters that Contributes to Quality of Urban Design	Royal Wharf	Fishguard Way	Key Takeaways from the Case Studies
<p>1. Accessibility to public transport</p>	<p>3 minutes away from DLR (Dockland Light Rail) makes it easily accessible and the bus station inside the development also makes it easy to travel around.</p>	<p>15 minutes away from DLR (Dockland Light Rail) and 12 mins away from the closest bus station makes it difficult for people to access public transportation.</p>	<p>Strong connectivity to public transportation makes it a desirable place for living. So location has its own role to play in property value.</p>
<p>2. Proximity to CBD</p>	<p>Both sites have close proximity to CBD as it's located in the same borough of Newham. The only difference is that Fishguard way is less accessible as compared to the Royal Wharf.</p>		<p>The close proximity to CBD means direct access to employment which may enhance property value.</p>
<p>3. Proximity to retail establishments</p>	<p>Royal Wharf has its own new local retail center which makes it convenient for residents for their daily shopping. Close proximity to public transportation also makes it easy to travel to the nearby major center or district center</p>	<p>Fishguard Way does not have any local shopping center within a 10-15 minutes walk so people have to travel for daily needs. And the site also does not have any bus station or tube station within 5 minutes walks so this makes it less accessible to nearby retail establishments.</p>	<p>Proximity to day to day shops has a huge role to play and provision of mixed use or retail within the development might attract more property value.</p>

Parameters that Contributes to Quality of Urban Design	Royal Wharf	Fishguard Way	Key Takeaways from the Case Studies
4. Proximity to Amenities	The masterplan has provision for high street development which allows development with different building uses like shopping center, barber shops, pharmacy, clinic, cafes, school, community centers and many more.	The development comprises only residential use buildings and does not have any other facilities so residents have to travel for basic needs.	Close proximity to shopping, school and community spaces can enhance quality of life and tend to fetch more property value.
5. Proximity to a view	The site is located on the bank of river Thames so it has direct access to the river. What makes Royal Wharf different is the whole boundary of the site on the riverbank is created in such a way that pedestrians can have an uninterrupted view to the river and barriers do not act as a visual barrier. Along with this protected vistas and visual nodes and links have been created to protect the view.	The site is located on the bank of river Thames so it has direct access to the river. The Fishguard Way is different as compared to the Royal Wharf because the barrier they have built along the river works as a visual barrier and pedestrians can not have direct view to the river. Residents have direct view to the river from their houses.	Views of any natural features or green space always have a role to play in property value. Royal wharf development can be a good example of how views can be protected and maximize the benefits.
6. Proximity to green space	Royal Wharf has a variety of green spaces within the site like square, park playground, linear park, pocket park and riverside walk and park which makes it a desirable place to be around and spend quality time outdoors. It also provides a view for residents which makes it more valuable. It also has provision for small retail with outdoor sittings next to the green space and river to make it more vibrant.	Fishguard Way has green spaces but it has more to do with ornamental rather than contributing to creating an active public realm. There are few benches along the river walk with a view to the wall which makes it less desirable for residents to go and spend time out there.	Green space, playgrounds and recreational spaces makes development more vibrant and tends to get higher prices for development.
7. Playgrounds and Recreational spaces			

Parameters that Contributes to Quality of Urban Design	Royal Wharf	Fishguard Way	Key Takeaways from the Case Studies
8. Active Frontages	Active frontages are a key to creating an active public realm. Royal wharf has a variety of edges to ensure the public realm and the private realms at the same time. Mixed use buildings on the high street and few small retail shops near the river make its edges vibrant and appealing.	The development comprises only residential use buildings and does not have any other uses that makes development very monotonous and it lacks an active public realm throughout the development.	Active building frontages can create an active public realm and create eyes on the street to make it safe for residents. Vibrant neighborhood may attract higher sales value compared to others.
9. Interconnected street networks with Fewer dead ends	The master plan has provision for different types of streets for vehicular movement. They have created different types of streets like primary streets with two lanes and parking spaces, secondary streets with one lane and tertiary streets to access homes and only accessible for residents to prioritize the pedestrian movement there is provision for walkways that makes it easy to navigate and creates a comfortable environment for pedestrians. As streets are interconnected with each other in hierarchy it's very convenient for people to move around. It also has provision for pedestrian only zones and restricted traffic movement to enhance the walking experience.	The site has restricted vehicular movement. There is a lake of pedestrian walkways on the primary access road within the site. Site does have a riverwalk with no vehicular movement but walking along the wall does not create an inevitable environment.	Clearly defined street networks with pedestrian walkways have influence on property value.
10. Improved sidewalks and walkability			

Parameters that Contributes to Quality of Urban Design	Royal Wharf	Fishguard Way	Key Takeaways from the Case Studies
11. Smaller blocks	The master plan provides viable residential structures that are permeable and visually accessible through small blocks rather than providing big impermeable urban blocks. For residents, a walking atmosphere is created through small, permeable urban blocks which produce a smooth urban grain.	The development has small permeable blocks which makes it easy to walk around.	Smaller blocks make it easier to navigate and walk around and it has human scale which doesn't make development impermeable and makes it visually accessible.
12. Housing Mix	Royal wharf consists of different typologies of houses like mixed use, apartments, flats and terraced houses with different range of tenures and plans. This brings a diverse population and building use and creates a different environment.	In the development there is only one typology of houses prevalent is apartment. Designing the development in this way restricts a rich mix of housing typologies and tenures to be developed within the area.	Diversity in typology and tenures attract different people from different income groups and create a diverse community. This may or may not have a relation with higher property value but it's always a good idea to have provision for different communities.

A synthesis of the outcomes derived from the analysis of these two distinct case studies provides a discerning perspective on the potential transformative impact of urban design qualities. It is apparent that the masterplan framework serves as an efficient means of facilitating the strategic integration of various design features, resulting in the formation of a development that is distinguished by its strong economic, environmental, and social components.

Comparative Property Price Analysis

The analysis of the variance in sales values between the two sites has been conducted using the Simple t-Tests method. This statistical approach facilitates a direct comparison of sales figures for both locations, yielding a calculated P value. This analytical process offers insights into the differences in sales performance.

The obtained results reveal a discernible discrepancy in sales values between Royal Wharf and Fishguard Way. Specifically, sales values for Royal Wharf exhibit a range spanning from 2000/sq.m to 10,000/sq.m, with an average sales value of 5,825. Conversely, the sales values for Fishguard Way fluctuate between 1800/sq.m and 6500/sq.m, with an average of 4100. It's noteworthy that the considered sales data pertains to recent years, from 2020 to 2023.

The disparity in average property values between the two sites is striking, with Royal Wharf outpacing Fishguard Way by a substantial 1725/sq.m. Moreover, the calculated P value derived from the T-test is noted to be 0.0481. Importantly, if the derived p-value falls below the chosen significance level of 0.05, the results of the statistical test can be deemed statistically significant. In this context, the observed p-value underpins the conclusion that a significant difference indeed exists between the sales values of the two sites.

In essence, the employment of the Simple t-Tests method has enabled the quantification of sales value discrepancies between Royal Wharf and Fishguard Way. The subsequent analysis and the derived p-value affirm the substantial divergence in sales values, establishing Royal Wharf as the site with notably higher average property values.

Sales Values for Royal Wharf

Figure 4.74: Sales Value in Royal Wharf.

Source: <https://housemetric.co.uk/map/SE10-o/> and Author's own illustrations

Sales Values for Fishguard Way

Figure 4.75: Sales Value in Fishguard Way.

Source: <https://housemetric.co.uk/map/SE10-0/> and Author's own illustrations

Comparitive Propert Price

Figure 4.76: Comparative Sales Values in Royal Wharf and Fishguard Way.

Source: <https://housemetric.co.uk/map/SE10-0/> and Author's own illustrations

Mean Value for Royal Wharf: 5825
Mean Value for Fishguard Way: 4100

P value (t-test for Equality of Means): 0.0481

If the p-value is less than chosen significance level (0.05), the result of the test can be considered statistically significant.

Next chapter discusses how these findings can be implicated in the Indian context and challenges and considerations.

05

Discussion

Implications for Indian Urban Planning

The primary goal of the research was to analyze whether urban design master plan led development in the residential sector led to greater property value enhancement compared to incremental growth strategies. The finding shows that Royal Wharf has generated more sales values than Fishguard Way, but this does not mean that masterplan led development is the only thing which has helped to generate high property value. Property values significantly depend on various factors which makes it difficult to analyze the effect of any one parameter on property value. But these findings demonstrate that there is a relation between masterplan led development and higher property values as different design qualities of master plan led development help to enhance property value.

To keep this in mind the findings that masterplan-led development yields higher property values compared to incremental growth in the UK have significant implications for urban planning practices in India. These insights can offer valuable guidance for decision-making, policy formulation, and development strategies within the Indian residential sector. The UK case study showcases the advantages of a comprehensive approach in urban development, as seen in masterplan-led strategies. Indian urban planning can benefit by moving away from isolated plot-level developments and embracing a holistic perspective. By adopting masterplan-led approaches, Indian cities can enhance property values while simultaneously addressing environmental, social, and economic concerns. Decision-makers can incorporate the UK's experience to foster a more integrated and forward-looking urban design framework as part of a larger urban planning framework. In order to establish urban design led masterplan framework there has to be an urban planning framework; as per cited in literature review that many indian cities are growing without city level master plan. After focusing on a city wide master plan cities can focus on an area based master plan to create vibrant areas for residents.

In the UK, planning permissions are required for strategic site development(master plan development) from local authorities, whereas in India there are site level planning permissions and guidelines are available. In order to carry out site specific masterplan there is strong need to have policies, guidelines and planning permission board to carry out master plan led development in India. Policy formulation in India could draw inspiration from the UK's emphasis on long-term vision and coordination. Developing policies that encourage masterplan-led development can lead to improved urban design, better infrastructure integration, and enhanced livability. The UK's successes and challenges can serve as valuable lessons to craft effective policies that balance private interests with broader societal needs, making Indian cities more resilient and sustainable.

The insights gained from the UK case study can inform development strategies in India's residential sector. Encouraging collaboration between various stakeholders, such as developers, planners, designers and local communities, can lead to more cohesive and impactful development outcomes. Integrating mixed-use spaces, green areas, and amenities within masterplans can enhance the quality of life for residents while boosting property values. By considering the UK's experience, India can strategize ways to accommodate population growth and urbanization while preserving cultural heritage and promoting equitable development.

The findings that masterplan-led development in the UK results in higher property values offer valuable implications for Indian urban planning. Incorporating lessons from the UK can guide Indian decision-makers in formulating effective policies, fostering collaboration, and developing strategies that lead to enhanced property values, sustainable urban growth, and improved quality of life for residents.

Benefits

Introducing a site-specific master plan as a stage between the Town Planning (TP) scheme and individual plot level development can have significant benefits and enhance the overall development process in India. This intermediate stage can address many of the coordination, alignment, and communication challenges that often arise between these two levels of planning. Here's how:

1. **Coordinated Transition:** A site-specific master plan can serve as a bridge between the broader regulations outlined in the TP scheme and the detailed design at the individual plot level. It allows for a smoother transition from the overarching vision to the practical implementation on the ground.
2. **Holistic Vision:** By adding an intermediate stage, the development process becomes more holistic. It enables planners to consider the entire site's potential and address concerns that might not be fully captured at either the TP scheme or individual plot levels. The site-specific master plan helps maintain consistency and continuity between the TP scheme and individual plot levels. It ensures that the essence of the broader planning objectives is preserved throughout the entire development process.
3. **Regulatory Alignment:** This stage can help align regulatory requirements and design guidelines with the specific site conditions, ensuring that the development is compliant with both the TP scheme and local context.
4. **Adaptability:** The site-specific master plan can be designed to incorporate flexibility and adaptability. As circumstances evolve, this stage allows for adjustments without disrupting the overall TP scheme or individual plot level developments.
5. **Higher-Quality Design:** A site-specific master plan allows for a more thoughtful and tailored approach to development. By considering the unique characteristics of the site, such as topography, views, and amenities, the resulting design can be more visually appealing and attractive to potential buyers or tenants. A site-specific master plan provides a visual representation of the development's layout, aiding stakeholders in understanding the intended design and making informed decisions.
6. **Amenities and Open Spaces:** Incorporating amenities like parks, green spaces, recreational facilities, and community areas into the site-specific master plan can create a more livable and enjoyable environment. These features can significantly enhance the perceived value of the property.
7. **Infrastructure and Connectivity:** Careful planning of infrastructure, transportation networks, and connectivity within the site-specific master plan can improve accessibility and convenience. Properties located in well-connected areas often command higher values.
8. **Mixed-Use Development:** Designing a site-specific master plan that accommodates mixed-use development, with a blend of residential, commercial, and recreational spaces, can create vibrant and dynamic neighborhoods. This diversity can contribute to increased property demand and value.
9. **Environmental Sustainability:** Incorporating sustainability principles into the site-specific master plan, such as energy-efficient design, green building practices, and conservation of natural resources, can attract environmentally conscious buyers and positively impact property values.
10. **Neighborhood Cohesion:** A site-specific master plan can promote a sense of community and neighborhood cohesion. Planned layouts that encourage interactions among residents can enhance the overall desirability of the area, which can influence property values.

11. **Architectural Aesthetics:** By guiding architectural styles and design guidelines, a site-specific master plan can ensure a harmonious and aesthetically pleasing built environment. Properties within such visually pleasing contexts often command premium prices.
12. **Market Differentiation:** Properties developed based on a site-specific master plan stand out in the market due to their unique design and features. This differentiation can attract buyers or tenants willing to pay a premium for a distinctive living experience.
13. **Public Perception:** A well-designed site-specific master plan can contribute to a positive public perception of the development. This positive image can translate into higher property values as potential buyers perceive the development as more desirable.
14. **Long-Term Value:** The thoughtful planning inherent in a site-specific master plan can result in enduring value. Properties that are part of a well-planned, cohesive community are likely to maintain their attractiveness over time, contributing to long-term property value appreciation.

Incorporating a site-specific master plan as an intermediate stage can strengthen the link between high-level urban planning goals and on-the-ground development. It provides a pragmatic and focused approach that allows for customization while maintaining alignment with broader urban planning strategies. Incorporating a site-specific master plan as an intermediary stage can contribute to a more holistic and value-driven development process. By focusing on creating an attractive and functional environment that aligns with the broader urban planning objectives, this approach has the potential to enhance property values and create desirable living spaces.

Challenges and Considerations in Indian Context

1. **Land Ownership and Fragmentation:** Land ownership in India can be fragmented, making it challenging to acquire and consolidate parcels of land for comprehensive development. Multiple landowners with differing interests can lead to delays and complications in the planning process.
2. **Regulatory and Bureaucratic Hurdles:** There are no specific policies and guidelines which help to promote masterplan led development. In order to promote masterplan led development in India there is a strong need to have policies, regulations, guidelines and government structure to regulate the development.
3. **Infrastructure Deficits:** Many areas in India lack basic infrastructure like water supply, sewage systems, and roads due to rapid urbanization. Integrating these essential services into a masterplan-led development can be costly and time-consuming, potentially affecting the feasibility of such projects.
4. **Resettlement and Rehabilitation:** In cases where existing communities need to be relocated to implement a masterplan, the process of resettlement and rehabilitation can be socially sensitive and legally challenging. Balancing the needs of the affected communities while executing the development can lead to conflicts and delays.
5. **Socioeconomic Disparities:** India has diverse socioeconomic demographics, and ensuring inclusivity in masterplan-led developments can be difficult. Addressing the needs of lower-income groups while maintaining the viability of the development can pose a significant challenge.
6. **Public Participation and Stakeholder Engagement:** Effective public participation and community engagement are crucial for successful masterplan-led development. However, involving a diverse range of stakeholders and addressing their concerns can be complex and time-consuming.

7. Funding and Financing: Securing adequate funding for large-scale masterplan projects can be difficult. Private investors may hesitate due to uncertainties in the market, and public funding might be constrained by competing priorities.

8. Political and Local Interests: Local politics and vested interests can influence the planning and execution of development projects. Political considerations can sometimes undermine long-term planning goals.

To overcome these obstacles, a combination of strategic planning, effective stakeholder engagement, transparent governance, adaptive regulations, and sustainable financing mechanisms would be essential. Additionally, learning from successful case studies, both within India and internationally, can provide valuable insights into how to navigate these challenges effectively.

06

Conclusion

In conclusion, the analysis conducted in the study suggests that there is a significant correlation between well-planned development and higher property values within the same area. While site planning undoubtedly plays a pivotal role in influencing property values, it's imperative to acknowledge the intricate interplay of various factors that contribute to this property value. Factors such as location, property size, neighborhood amenities, market trends, appearance, building quality and economic conditions must be taken into account to form a comprehensive understanding of the observed trends. Therefore, while well-planned sites do exhibit higher property values, the broader landscape of influences mandates a nuanced interpretation of the findings. This research underscores the importance of holistic assessment and highlights the need for further studies to delve into the intricate dynamics shaping property values within a given locality.

In this comprehensive study utilizing the sales comparison approach, it becomes evident that well-planned sites do indeed hold a substantial association with higher property values in the same geographical area. The empirical evidence gathered underscores the significance of meticulous site planning in the realm of real estate valuation. However, the intricacies of property valuation necessitate a cautious and well-balanced interpretation of these findings.

While site planning emerges as a key driver, it is imperative to recognize the intricate web of factors that collectively contribute to property values. Beyond the astute arrangement of infrastructure and amenities, location remains an undeniable influencer, with proximity to essential services, transportation hubs, and desirable neighborhoods playing a pivotal role. The dimensions of property size and layout are intricately intertwined with the equation, further underscoring that a holistic perspective is indispensable.

Market trends, often dictated by prevailing economic conditions, exert an undeniable force on property values. The flow of demand, influenced by socioeconomic factors, investor sentiment, and overall market stability, cannot be overlooked. Additionally, the presence of future development potential and regulatory considerations can add layers of complexity to the valuation landscape.

In light of these multifaceted determinants, the linkage between well-planned sites and higher property values must be understood as a dynamic component within a larger ecosystem. This study, while shedding light on the crucial role of site planning, beckons for a continued exploration into the nuanced interactions between these diverse factors. A comprehensive understanding of property valuation demands a meticulous dissection of each contributing element and an acknowledgment that no single variable operates in isolation.

Therefore, while the data underscores the positive correlation between well-planned sites and enhanced property values, it is essential to approach this conclusion with a measured degree of critical thinking. It is through this lens of comprehensive assessment that a more accurate, robust, and insightful understanding of real estate valuation emerges, guiding both practitioners and policymakers in making informed decisions within this intricate realm.

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University of Westminster
University Research Ethics Committee

Application for Research Ethics Consideration*

PART A

Section 1 – PROJECT AND APPLICANT DETAILS	
1.1 Project Title: Unveiling the Advantages of Master Plan Development over Incremental Growth for Residential Sector in Enhancing Property Value	
1.2 Applicant Details	
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Faculty: DCDI	
Please check the relevant box:	
Undergraduate <input type="checkbox"/>	Postgraduate <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
MPhil/PhD Student <input type="checkbox"/>	Staff <input type="checkbox"/>
I confirm I have read the <i>University's Code of Practice Governing the Ethical Conduct of Research</i>	YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/>
1.3 Supervisor/Dean of Faculty/Faculty Research Director details	
Please note that all applicants with a supervisor(s) must ensure that the supervisor signs the declaration at the bottom of this page if completing Part A only or in Section 10.3 if completing Part B	
All staff must ensure that their Dean of Faculty, or Faculty Research Director (or nominee), as appropriate, signs the declaration at the bottom of this page if completing Part A only or in Section 10.3 if completing Part B	
Name: (signed) Andrew Boughton	University Email Address: A.Boughton@westminster.ac.uk
Faculty: DCDI	Telephone Number: +44 7711177889

NOW PLEASE COMPLETE THE REMAINDER OF PART A (* Part A is a self-assessment form used to ascertain whether you have ethical implications in your work. Part A is not an Application for Consideration by University Research Ethics Committee (UREC) unless specified when submitting. Part B is the Application for Ethical Approval and when submitting, it should have a Cover Sheet and Part A attached in all cases).

PART A (Continued)

Section 2 – Project Details

2.1 Please provide a description of the background with references to relevant literature (250 words maximum):

The research aims to investigate various aspects of master plan development in relation to urban design qualities to determine their impact on property value. Additionally, the study will analyze existing urban design and planning practices to assess their influence on property values. The findings from this research will aid in improving urban design practices in India's development projects.

This research is useful for several reasons. Firstly, by investigating the benefits of urban design in India and its impact on residential property values, it aims to fill a gap in existing knowledge. The limited emphasis on urban design in India makes it crucial to provide evidence that supports the hypothesis of urban design qualities improving property value.

Secondly, the findings of this research can have implications for urban planning and development in India. If the hypothesis is proven, it would highlight the importance of incorporating urban design principles and qualities in residential projects. This could lead to more aesthetically pleasing and functional urban environments, enhancing the overall quality of life for residents.

Furthermore, demonstrating the positive relationship between urban design qualities and property value can attract attention from policymakers, real estate developers, and investors. It could serve as a catalyst for promoting and prioritizing urban design as an integral component of urban development strategies in India, ultimately leading to more sustainable and desirable urban spaces.

Lastly, this research can empower homeowners, buyers, and investors by providing valuable insights into the factors that contribute to property value. Understanding the impact of urban design qualities on property values can inform decision-making processes.

The findings of this research will provide valuable insights for urban planners, real estate developers, and policymakers, informing them about the importance of incorporating certain design qualities in urban development projects. Overall, this research holds significance in expanding knowledge, influencing urban planning practices, and empowering stakeholders in making informed decisions regarding urban design and residential property.

2. Please provide a brief description and the aims of your study (250 words maximum):

The aim of this study is to explore the benefits of urban design-led master plan development in comparison to incremental growth approaches within the residential sector, specifically in terms of enhancing property values.

2.3. Please outline the design and methodology of your study (include details of the selection and recruitment of participants (if any) and details of any invasive (e.g. blood samples, inhalation/ingestion of food and/or non-food products (in abnormally higher or lower levels than normal or a different form), or intrusive (e.g. questionnaires, focus groups, interviews, etc.) procedures [attach extra information as necessary] (400 words maximum in total):

Appendix

2.4. Timescales

Start Date (DD/MM/YY): 01/06/2023

Estimated duration of work: 3 months (24th August)

Appendix

Section 3 - RISK OF HARM				
NOTE 1: Where indicated below applicants should check if the research will require ethical approval from a National Research Ethics Committee via the <u>Integrated Research Application System (IRAS)</u> - nres_queries@nhs.net - http://www.hra-decisiontools.org.uk/ethics/				
NOTE 2: The University of Westminster holds a Human Tissue Authority Licence – This licence is specifically for tissue stored at 115 New Cavendish Street in accordance with the terms of the licence – Advice must be obtained from the University Human Tissue Authority Officer				
RISK OF HARM (to self, colleagues, participants, environment or animals)		Yes	No	N/A
1	Will any pain or more than mild discomfort result from the study?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Could the study induce any psychological stress or anxiety or cause harm or negative consequences beyond the risks encountered in normal life?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Will the study involve prolonged or repetitive physical or psychological testing of human participants that may put someone at risk, e.g. use of treadmill?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Will the study involve raising sensitive topics (e.g. sexual activity, drug use, revelation of medical history, bereavement, illegal activities, etc.)?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Does your work involve any "relevant material" containing human cells (e.g. blood, urine, saliva, body tissues but NOT established cell-lines) from living or deceased persons (Such work must take account of the Human Tissue Act)? – See Note 1 and 2 above.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6	Will DNA samples be taken from human participants (Such work must take account of the Human Tissue Act)? – See Note 1 and 2 above.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7	Does your study raise any issues of personal safety for you or other researchers or participants involved in the project (Especially relevant if taking place outside working hours or off University premises)?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
8	Does your study involve deliberately misleading the participants (e.g. deception, covert observation)?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
9	Does your work involve administration of a food or non-food substance of a different type from or in abnormally higher or lower amounts than normal or one that is known to cause allergic reaction(s) or potential psychological stress?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
10	Does your study involve issues relating to personal and/or sensitive data?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
PARTICIPANTS (and/or their records/associated data)		Yes	No	N/A
Does your work involve any of the following:				
11	Human participants in a health and/or social care setting (e.g. patients, those attending day centres, community care, rehabilitation centres, etc., including in the NHS, other public, private and/or voluntary sectors)? – See Note 1 above.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
12	Human participants who may be deemed vulnerable (e.g. children, people in poverty and/or with physiological or psychological impairments, persons attending rehabilitation centres, persons in easily identifiable positions that could be subject to victimisation, etc.)?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
13	Expectant or new mothers?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
14	Refugees/Asylum seekers?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
15	Minors (under the age of 18 years old)?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
16	Participants in custody (e.g. prisoners or arrestees)? – See Note 1 above.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
17	Participants with impaired mental capacity (e.g. severe mental illness, brain damage, sectioned under Mental Health Act, lowered or reduced sense of consciousness)? – See Note 1 above.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
18	Animals (or animal tissue).	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
INFORMATION TO PARTICIPANTS		Yes	No	N/A
19	Will you provide participants with a Participant Information Sheet prior to obtaining informed consent which can be taken away by the participant?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
20	Will you describe the procedures to participants in advance, so that they are informed about what to expect?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
21	Will you obtain informed consent for participation (normally written)? OR in the case of using personal data previously acquired was consent given for the reuse of the data for other research purposes?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
22	Will you tell participants that they may withdraw from the research at any time and for any reason without any impact on their care, service provision etc.?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
23	Will you give participants the option of omitting questions they do not want to answer?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
24	Will you tell participants that their data will be treated as confidential and that, if published, it will not be identifiable as theirs?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
25	Will you offer feedback to participants at the end of their participation, upon request (e.g. give them a brief explanation of the study and its outcomes)?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
26	Has external funding or collaboration been applied for/received, which requires institutional ethical consideration or approval?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

